

the **23**rd INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
**LIFE SCIENCES FOR
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT**
26-28 September 2024, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

PROGRAM

BOOKLET

The 23rd International Conference

”LIFE SCIENCES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT”

**26th– 28th September, 2024
Cluj-Napoca, Romania**

**University of Agricultural Sciences and
Veterinary Medicine of
Cluj-Napoca**

PROGRAM BOOKLET

The 23rd International Conference

”LIFE SCIENCES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT”

Organized by:

University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of
Cluj-Napoca

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5. Murat FINDIK, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Ondokuz, Mayis, Turkey
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7. Tolga GUVENC, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Ondokuz, Mayis, Turkey
8. Leonardo MEOMARTINO, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Naples, Italy
9. Miguel Moreno MILAN, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Cordoba, Spain
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14. Vladimir CELER, University of Veterinary and Pharmaceutical Sciences Brno, Czech Republic
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CONFERENCE TIMETABLE

Thursday, 26 th September 2024		
09:00 -11:00	Registration of participants	Hall - Aula Magna “Mihai Şerban”, UASMV Cluj-Napoca
09:00 -11:00	Poster Display <i>(For more details, please see the program)</i>	
09:30-09:45	Opening ceremony Rector, Cornel CĂTOI Vice-Rector, Vlad MUREŞAN	Aula Magna “Mihai Şerban”, UASMV Cluj-Napoca
09:45-12:40	Plenary Session Chairpersons: Sanda ANDREI, Cătălina DAN, Oana POP, Mignon SANDOR, Adriana URCAN Horia VLASIN	Aula Magna “Mihai Şerban”, UASMV Cluj-Napoca
09:45-10:10	LEARNING FROM INNOVATIONS IN EUROPEAN FARMING SYSTEMS: EVIDENCE FROM SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENTS WITH THE PUBLIC GOODS TOOL	LAURENCE SMITH United Kingdom
10:10-10:35	FARM ANIMAL WELFARE IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT	JENNY YNGVESSON Sweden
10:35-11:00	PAPILLOMAVIRUS INFECTION IN RUMINANTS AND HORSES: NEW INSIGHTS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES	FRANCO ROPERTO Italy
11:00-11:25	FROM WASTE TO WEALTH : BIOCONVERSION OF XYLAN FROM SUGAR CANE BAGASSE INTO FUNCTIONAL XYLO-OLIGOSACCHARIDES (XOS)	MONTAROP YAMABHAI Thailand
11:25-11:50	YEAST'S CONTRIBUTION TO MELATONIN FORMATION FOR BOOST WINE'S NUTRITIONAL VALUE	Valeriu COTEA Romania
11:50-12:15	3D CADASTRE - A TOOL FOR FIT FOR PURPOSE LAND ADMINISTRATION	NIKOLA VUČIĆ Croatia
12:15-12:40	INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION AND MULTILINGUALISM IN AGRICULTURAL SCIENCE – A SCHOLARLY JOURNAL EXAMPLE	ZVONIMIR PRPIC Croatia
13:00 –14:30	<i>Lunch – Biodiversity Research Center</i>	
15:00-18:30	Oral Sessions (sessions I-X) <i>For more details, please see the program</i>	
19:00-24:00	Gala Dinner (Restaurant Wonderland Resort)	
Friday, 27 th September 2024		
09:00-12:30	Poster Presentation and Evaluation Oral Sessions (sessions I-X) <i>For more details, please see the program</i>	
12:30-13:00	<i>Break</i>	
13:00 –13:10	Closing ceremony and Best Poster Awards	Aula Magna “Mihai Şerban”, UASMV Cluj-Napoca
Saturday, 28 th September 2024		
08:30-21:00	Post - conference tour (optional) - Transylvania Route: Alba-Carolina Citadel and Apoldia Vineyard & Winery Fest	

Conference proceedings

The participants registered to our conference have the opportunity not only to present their results, published as summary in the “Book of Abstracts” but also to publish *in extenso* their contributions. The oral presentations, after a previous peer review process, can be published in the journal Bulletin of UASVM-CN– Agriculture, Horticulture, Animal Science-Biotechnologies, Veterinary Medicine and Food Science and Technology, Forestry and Cadastre. To mention, the Bulletin UASVM-CN are indexed in prestigious international databases:

- AGRIS (<https://agris.fao.org/agris-search/index.do>)
- DOAJ (<https://www.doaj.org/>)
- Clarivate - Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI) (https://mjl.clarivate.com:/search-results?issn=2344-2344&hide_exact_match_fl=true&utm_source=mjl&utm_medium=share-by-link&utm_campaign=search-results-share-this-journal)
- ASOS indeks (<https://asosindex.com.tr/>)
- Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.com/>)
- INDEX COPERNICUS (<https://journals.indexcopernicus.com/search/details?id=12593>)
- InfoBase (<https://www.infobase.com/>)
- AGRIS - International System for Agricultural Science and Technology (<https://agris.fao.org/>)

Opening ceremony

The opening ceremony will be held Thursday, 26th September 2024, from 09:30-09:45 at Aula Magna “Mihai Șerban”, UASVM Cluj-Napoca.

Thursday, 26th September 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

Session 1 and 2: Agriculture and Environmental Protection

Hall A4, Rectorate Building

15:00 – 18:30 ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Chairman: Assoc. Prof. Jake MOWRER, PhD

Moderator: Prof. Teodor RUSU, PhD

Assoc. Prof. Vlad STOIAN, PhD

BIOFUMIGATION WITH MUSTARD (*BRASSICACEAE*) CAN ALTER NITROGEN MINERALIZATION AND NITRIFICATION OF ORGANIC FERTILIZERS

Reshma RAMACHANDRAN, Jake MOWRER

THE INFLUENCE OF THE USE OF GREEN MANURES ON THE ATTACK OF PATHOGENS ON WHEAT

Peter-Balázs ÁCS, Ioan PĂCURAR

THE INFLUENCE OF SOME TECHNOLOGICAL FACTORS ON THE PRODUCTION OF TRITICALE

Beniamin-Emanuel ANDRAȘ, Marcel M. DUDA

DETERMINATION OF QUALITATIVE INDICATORS OF WORK IN THE APPLICATION OF SOLID CHEMICAL FERTILIZERS

Roland-Sandor DEJÓ, Ovidiu MARIAN, Ovidiu RANTA, Alexandru GHETȚE

INVASIVE SPECIES *CORYTHUCHA CILIATA* SAY AND *CORYTHUCHAARCUATA* SAY - REVIEW

Diana DRĂGAN, Arnilva MARA, Horia BUNESCU, Ionuț- Bogdan HULUJAN1, Teodora FLORIAN

ASSESSING THE POTENTIAL FOR HYDROGEL PRODUCTION FROM FLAX SEEDS

Claudia BALINT, Antonia ODAGIU, Petru BURDUHOS, Alexandra MUREȘAN

INNOVATIVE SOIL WATER RETENTION TECHNOLOGIES DURING DROUGHT: A REVIEW

Petru-Daniel BURDUHOS, Antonia ODAGIU, Claudia BALINT, Bianca MOLDOVAN, Cristian IEDERAN, Ioan BRAȘOVEAN

16:20 – 16:40 COFEE BREAK

COMPARISON OF DENSITIES AND FEATURES OF LEAF PELTATE GLANDULAR TRICHOMES IN FOUR *SALVIA* SPECIES

Robert Adrian HAAS, Ioana CRIȘAN, Dan VÂRBAN, Rodica VÂRBAN

POLLUTANTS REMOVAL USING COST EFFECTIVE MATERIAL FROM APPLE WASTES

Alin CÂRDAN, Maria-Loredana SORAN, Ildiko LUNG, Ocsana OPRIȘ, Adina STEGARESCU, Irina KACSO, Maria MIHEȚ, Alexandru TURZA, Dmitry LAZACOVICH, Aliona GHENDOV-MOȘANU, Rodica STURZA, Cristina MORMILE, Francesco MASCHIO, Fabio VENTURI, Alessio CALABRÒ, Stefano BELLUCI, Delia GLIGOR

THE EFFECT OF DIFFERENT STRESSORS ON PLANT'S PHYSIOLOGIC PARAMETERS AND SECONDARY METABOLITES

Lucian COPOLOVICI, Andreea LUPITU, Flavia BORTES, Maria COJOCARU-TOMA, Angelica OHINDOVSKI, Mihaela NARTEA, Cristian MOISA, Dana COPOLOVICI

TRANSFER CAPACITY OF SOME POLLUTANTS - HEAVY METALS FROM SOIL TO *PRUNUS SP.*

Claudiu-Denis FILIP, Mirela Ana COMAN

EXPLORING THE NUTRITIONAL SIGNIFICANCE OF WILD MUSHROOMS: A CASE STUDY OF *BOLETUS EDULIS* AND *CANTHARELLUS CIBARIUS*

Alexandra-Cristina MUREȘAN, Antonia ODAGIU, Claudia BALINT

STUDY REGARDING METHODS AND TECHNIQUES USED FOR ANALYSIS OF SPRAY DRIFT AND DROPLET SIZE DISTRIBUTION BY AGRICULTURAL SPRAYING MACHINES

Adrian MOLNAR-IRIMIE, Ovidiu RANTA, SORIN STĂNILĂ, Ovidiu MARIAN

COMPREHENSIVE NOISE RISK ASSESSMENT IN HIGH-DENSITY URBAN AREAS: IMPLICATIONS FOR PUBLIC HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT

Antonia ODAGIU, Claudia BALINT, Bianca MOLDOVAN, CRISTIAN IEDERAN, DRAGOȘ OROIAN

MICA BASED METAL-OXIDE ADSORBENTS FOR WATER PURIFICATION

Stelian PINTEA, Adina STEGARESCU, Ildiko LUNG, Ocsana OPRIȘ, Maria MIHEȚ, Alexandru TURZA, Septimiu TRIPON, Maria-Loredana SORAN, Maria PRUNEAN, Delia GLIGOR

Thursday, 26th September 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

Session 3: Food Science and Technology

Hall A2, Rectorate Building

15:00 – 18:30 ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Chairperson: Assoc. Prof. Laura STAN, PhD
Moderator: Lect. Corina Anca FĂRCAȘ, PhD
Secretary: Oana NEGREAN, Master student

USING EXTERNAL FIELDS TO RECOVER MICROALGAL FUNCTIONAL INGREDIENTS

Ruoxi ZHANG, Jacques KIEFFER, Michel EPPINK, Rene WIJFFELS, Vittorio SAGGIOMO, Iulian Z. BOBOESCU

OXIDOREDUCTASE-BASED BIOSENSORS FOR FOOD APPLICATIONS

Dietmar HALTRICH

COMPARISON OF STRUCTURAL BEHAVIOR IN THE PROCESS DYNAMICS OF THREE DIFFERENT OLEOGEL BASED MEAT PRODUCTS

Anda Elena TANISLAV, Anca Alexandra CORNEA, Dorin ȚIBULCĂ, Maria-Ioana SOCACIU, Cristina Anamaria SEMENIUC, Francisc DULF, Elena MUDURA and Vlad MUREȘAN

EXPLORING THE PHYTOCHEMICAL AND PHYSICAL STABILITY OF ANTHOCYANINS, PHYCOCYANIN, AND BETACYANIN IN A CHEESECAKE PRODUCT

Călina CIONT (NAGY), Cristina SELIN, Anda TANISLAV, Bernadette-Emőke TELEKY, Florica RANGA, Vlad MUREȘAN, Andruța MUREȘAN, Dan Cristian VODNAR, Oana Lelia POP

PARTIAL LEAST SQUARES DISCRIMINANT ANALYSIS (PLS-DA) MODEL FOR EGGS DIFFERENTIATION ACCORDING TO HEN'S GROWING SYSTEM

Gabriela CRISTEA, Adriana DEHELEAN, Ariana-R. HATEGAN, Romulus PUȘCAȘ

THE ROLE AND IMPACT OF NUTRACEUTICALS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF METABOLIC SYNDROME: AN INTEGRATED APPROACH

Cristina Georgiana MARCHIȘ, Călina CIONT (NAGY), Ramona SUHAROSCHI, Oana Lelia POP

IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS IN EXPANDED RICE PRODUCTS

Mădălina O. MARINCAȘ, Romina A. MARC, Crina C. MUREȘAN

INVESTIGATION OF PHYTOCHEMICAL COMPOUNDS IN APPLE FRUIT FROM WILD SPECIES, TRADITIONAL AND MODERN VARIETIES USING ADVANCED ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUES

Alexandra Mădălina MATEESCU, Andruța E. MUREȘAN, Vlad MUREȘAN, Radu E. SESTRAS, Adriana F. SESTRAS, Sevastița MUSTE, Adriana PĂUCEAN, Marcel DUDA

CITRUS ESSENTIAL OILS NANO-EMULSIONS: FROM A TOXICOLOGICAL POINT OF VIEW

Mădălina MEDELEANU, Antonio CASCAJOSA, Silvia PICHARO, Ana Belen CEREZO, Giorgiana CĂTUNESCU, Sonia SOCACI

DESIGNING THE TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS FOR PRODUCING CHOCOLATE BONBONS WITH MARZIPAN USING PETRI NETS

Ion Dan MIRONESCU, Ioana PICIU, Monica MIRONESCU

USE OF CHOCOLATE AS SUPPORT FOR NATURAL BIOACTIVE INGREDIENTS

Monica MIRONESCU, Ciprian JOSAN, Ion Dan MIRONESCU, Cecilia GEORGESCU, Szintia JEVCSAK, Endre MATHE

IMPACT OF ACID AND ALKALINE PRETREATMENTS ON WHEAT BRAN NUTRITIONAL QUALITY AND BIOACTIVITY

Silvia-Amalia NEMES, Bernadette-Emőke TELEKY, Lavinia-Florina CĂLINOIU, Deborah-Gertrude-Alice ELEKES, Diana PLĂMADĂ, Anca Corina FARCAȘ, Răzvan ODOCHEANU, Laura MITREA, Mihaela Stefana PASCUTA, SZABO Katalin, Anita VARVARA, Bianca STEFANESCU, Ana-Maria COCEAN, Adrian Gheorghe MARTAU, Francisc-Vasile DULF, Dan-Cristian VODNAR

FREQUENCY OF *E. COLI* IN MILK AND DAIRY PRODUCTS

Lucia Elena PANAIT, Roxana VIDICAN

NUTRITION IN THE CONTEXT OF SUSTAINABILITY: THE IMPACTS OF THE PLANT-BASED DIETS

Andreea PAVEL, Mădălina CHIOREAN and Ramona SUHAROSCHI

MAPPING THE INTERPLAY BETWEEN PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS, GUT MICROBIOTA, AND BIOTRANSFORMATION

Diana PLĂMADĂ, Bernadette-Emőke TELEKY, Silvia Amalia NEMEȘ, Laura MITREA, Katalin SZABO, Lavinia-Florina CĂLINOIU, Mihaela Stefana PĂȘCUȚA, Rodica-Anita VARVARA, Călina CIONT (NAGY), Ana-Maria COCEAN, Răzvan ODOCHEANU, Gheorghe Adrian MARTĂU, Francisc Vasile DULF, Dan Cristian VODNAR

THE FUNCTIONALITY OF A MIXTURE OF PEA/SOY PROTEIN ISOLATES AND GUMS AS AFFECTED BY THERMAL DENATURATION IN DEVELOPING FAT REPLACING SYSTEMS

Andreea PUȘCAȘ, Anda Tanislav, Anca Fărcaș, Andruța MUREȘAN, Vlad MUREȘAN

ACORNS (*QUERCUS* SPP.) - CHEMICAL AND STRUCTURAL INSIGHTS

Eugen Dan RADU, Teodora Emilia COLDEA, Vlad MUREȘAN, Corina Maria ȘUTEA, Edward MUNTEAN, Floricuța RANGĂ, Dorina SIMEDRU, Elena MUDURA

Thursday, 26th September 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

JOINT SESSION
HORTICULTURE AND ECONOMICS

HALL: Blue Amphitheatre – 2nd Floor, ICHAT

15.00-16.15 ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Chairman: Prof. Mugurel JITEA, PhD
Moderators: Prof. Felix ARION, PhD
Assoc. Prof. Catalina DAN, PhD

PARTICIPATORY APPROACHES FOR SUSTAINABLE LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION

Agnes VAN DEN POL-VAN DASSELAAR

PLANTS BIOSTIMULANTS AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN A CLIMATE CHANGE SCENARIO

Javier ZUZUNAGA ROSAS, Monica BOSCAIU, Oscar VICENTE

SPECIAL FERTILIZERS USED IN HORTICULTURE (ORNAMENTAL PLANTS AND LAWN)

Răzvan BULUGEA, Mihaela CHETELEȘ

Session 4: Horticulture

HALL: Blue Amphitheatre – 2nd Floor, ICHAT

16.15-18.30 ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Chairman: Prof. Oscar VICENTE, PhD
Moderators: Prof. Dimitrios BILALIS, PhD
Assoc. Prof. Catalina DAN, PhD

CONVERSION OF A VASE CANOPY INTO A PLANAR PARALLEL U IN AN ALMOND ORCHARD – PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Mihaela BĂLUȚĂ, Florin STĂNICĂ

BREEDING A NEW APPLE HYBRID POPULATION WITH THE *VF* GENE THROUGH MARKER-ASSISTED SELECTION

Georgeta Maria BIVOLARIU (GUZU), Ioan ZAGRAI, Claudiu MOLDOVAN, Luminița Antonela ZAGRAI, Anca Maria CHIOREAN, Mirela Irina CORDEA

THE EFFECT OF NITROGEN FERTILIZATION ON QUALITY INDICES OF RASPBERRY YIELD IN RELATION TO HIGH TEMPERATURES

Diana Elena BOLOHAN, Ioana BUȚERCHI, Lucian RĂUS

THE RESPONSE OF SOME SWEET CHERRY CULTIVARS TO THE ATTACK OF MINING LARVAE AND MOTHS IN THE ECOLOGICAL CONDITIONS OF NORTHWEST ROMANIA

Daniel CALANCEA, Cătălina DAN, Adriana F. SESTRAS, Mădălina MILITARU, Radu E. SESTRAS

THE EFFECTS OF CLIMATE CHANGES ON THE PHENOLOGY OF SOME CHOKEBERRY (*ARONIA MELANOCARPA*) CULTIVARS

Anca Maria CHIOREAN, Zsolt JAKAB- ILYEFALVI, Smaranda ROȘU- MAREȘ, Georgeta GUZU, Claudiu MOLDOVAN, Ioan ZAGRAI, Mirela Irina CORDEA

CHARACTERIZATION OF GRAPEVINE GENOTYPES BY SIMPLE SEQUENCE REPEATS (SSR) MARKERS AND DEVELOPMENT OF A MICROSATELITE DNA-BASED BARCODES DESIGN

Monica HÂRȚA, Rodica POP, Liliana ROTARU, Alin Ionel DOBREI, Doina CLAPA

EFFICACY OF SOME BIOLOGICAL AND CONVENTIONAL PRODUCTS IN FIRE BLIGHT MANAGEMENT IN *MALUS DOMESTICA* BORKH.

Smaranda Doina ROȘU-MAREȘ, Ioan ZAGRAI, Claudiu MOLDOVAN, Anca Maria CHIOREAN, Georgeta GUZU, Zsolt JAKAB- ILYEFALVI

ASSESSMENT OF GENETIC STABILITY AMONG MICRO PROPAGATED *PRUNUS DULCIS* PLANTLETS USING SCOT MARKERS IN DUHOK PROVINCE KURDISTAN REGION, IRAQ

Diana SALEH, Jaladet JUBRAEL, Mosleh SALEH DUHOKY

BUCKWHEAT (*FAGOPYRUM ESCULENTUM* L.) CULTIVATION UNDER DROUGHT STRESS

Panteleimon STAVROPOULOS, Aikaterini SARSENTOU, Konstantinos PANTALEON, Sotiria PATSIALI, Antonios MAVROEIDIS, Ioannis ROUSSIS, Ioanna KAKABOUKI

Thursday, 26th September 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

JOINT SESSION
HORTICULTURE AND ECONOMICS

HALL: Blue Amphitheatre – 2nd Floor, ICHAT

15.00-16.15 ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Chairman: Prof. Mugurel JITEA, PhD
Moderators: Prof. Felix ARION, PhD
Assoc. Prof. Catalina DAN, PhD

PARTICIPATORY APPROACHES FOR SUSTAINABLE LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION

Agnes VAN DEN POL-VAN DASSELAAR

PLANTS BIOSTIMULANTS AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN A CLIMATE CHANGE SCENARIO

Javier ZUZUNAGA ROSAS, Monica BOSCAIU, Oscar VICENTE

SPECIAL FERTILIZERS USED IN HORTICULTURE (ORNAMENTAL PLANTS AND LAWN)

Răzvan BULUGEA, Mihaela CHETELEȘ

Session 5: Economics and Rural Development

HALL: Library – 1st Floor, ICHAT

16.15-18.30 ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Chairman: Prof. Felix ARION, PhD
Moderators: Prof. Agnes VAN DEN POL-VAN DASSELAAR, PhD
Prof. Silvius STANCIU, PhD

ECOMUSEUM OF ȚARA MOȚILOR. A SUSTAINED EFFORT TO SAFEGUARD THE SURROUNDING LANDSCAPE AND FOSTER RURAL DEVELOPMENT WITHIN THE APUSENI NATURAL PARK

Felix H. ARION, Alin MOS, Oana BRINZAN, Iulia Diana ARION

FOOD PRODUCT INCIDENTS: AN ANALYSIS OF WITHDRAWALS AND RECALLS ON THE ROMANIAN MARKET

Silvius STANCIU

TURN AROUND, DON'T DROWN" - LESSONS LEARNT FROM THE 2023 FLOOD IN MAGNESIA, GREECE

Efthimios BAKOGIANNIS, Konstantina-Despoina ATHANASIA, Anna DIONYSOPOULOU, Gabriela PLAKA, Vasilleios SIDIRAS, Maria XIROGIANNIS, Charalampos KYRIAKIDIS

FROM EAST TO WEST: INTERNATIONAL TRADE AND TRANSFORMATIONS IN MOLDOVA'S AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

Liliana CIMPOIES, Adrian COJOCARU

SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF ROMANIAN GRAZING FARMS. PRELIMINARY RESULTS FROM GRAZING4AGROECOLOGY FARM SELFASSESEMENT TOOL

Ionel Mugurel JITEA, Adrian GLIGA, Daniel CHICIUDEAN, Vlad ISARIE, Valentin MIHAI, Felix ARION, Diana E. DUMITRAȘ

PROPOSING A NEW QUALITY LABEL CERTIFYING GRAZING PRODUCTS IN ROMANIA

Filippo ZAFFARONI, Nattida KANCHANAKUL, Blandine LACOMBE, Zeeshan RASHEED, Vlad ISARIE, Felix H. ARION

SUPPORTING THE CERTIFICATION PROCESS OF A PGI CHEESE IN TRANSYLVANIA

Cherry VILLACORTA, Emmanuel Kwofie, Mercy KILEL, Fabiana IRIGOYEN, Felix H. ARION

SCENARIOS REGARDING COVERING THE RISKS FOR THE GARLIC CULTURE IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

Ancuța MARIN, Diana-Maria ILIE, Steliana RODINO, Vili DRAGOMIR, Rozi Liliana BEREVOIANU

DISTINCTIVE ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF MOUNTAIN REGIONS AND COMPREHENSIVE STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE DIVERSIFICATION

Rebeca Claudia CHIRILĂ, Ramona Vasilica BACTER, Iulia Cristina MUREȘAN

EXPLORING INNOVATIVE PASTURE MANAGEMENT AND CERTIFICATION POTENTIAL IN ROMANIA WITHIN A EUROPEAN FRAMEWORK

Vlad ISARIE, Felix ARION

QUALITY SCHEMES IN THE VIEW OF TELEMEEA CHEESE CONSUMERS IN ROMANIA: DRIVER OF CHANGE FOR COMPETITIVE MARKETING STRATEGIES

Corina A. MAREȘ, Diana E. DUMITRAȘ

ANALYSIS OF THE VALUE CHAIN OF ORGANIC GRAINS. A ROMANIAN CASE STUDY

Iulia Sorina DAN, Ionel Mugurel JITEA

A REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE REGARDING THE FOOD SYSTEM APPROACH IN EUROPE

Raluca BARBU, Diana DUMITRAȘ

**PROFILING NATURE-BASED TOURISTS VISITING NATIONAL AND NATURAL
PARKS OF ROMANIA: PRELIMINARY RESULTS**

Delia DONICI, Diana DUMITRAȘ

**THE USAMV CLUJ-NAPOCA LIBRARY - SUPPORT FOR THE TRAINING OF
FUTURE SPECIALISTS TO RESPOND TO THE GOALS OF SUSTAINABLE RURAL
DEVELOPMENT**

Cristina Florica SELICEAN, Marioara ILEA

Thursday, 26th September 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

Session 6 and 7: Animal Science and Biotechnologies

Hall: Red Amphitheater, Library Building

15:00 – 18:30 ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Chairman: Assoc. Prof. Cristian Ovidiu Coroian, PhD
Moderator: Lect. Mihai Şuteu, PhD
Secretary: Assist. Alexandru Deac, PhD

CeGaT – YOUR GENETIC AND SEQUENCING EXPERTS

Oana VOLOACĂ

EU PIG FARM WELFARE: NAVIGATING CHALLENGES AND EMBRACING OPPORTUNITIES

Ioan I. LADOŞI, Daniela LADOŞI, Aurelia COROIAN, Alexandru DEAC, Tudor PĂPUC Raul SAVIN, Marius ZĂHAN

LOW-PROTEIN DIET BALANCED FOR ESSENTIAL AMINO ACIDS SHOWS ENVIRONMENTAL AND ECONOMIC ADVANTAGE IN DAIRY PRODUCTION

Antal VIGH, Jessie GUYADER, Claudia PARYS

STUDY ON THE GROWTH PERFORMANCE OF RAINBOW TROUT (*ONCORHYNCHUS MYKISS*) FED WITH *TENEBRIO MOLITOR* LARVAE

Camelia RĂDUCU, Paul UIUIU, Daniel COCAN, Radu CONSTANTINESCU, Vioara MIREŞAN, Camelia MUNTEANU, Corina HULUBA, Andrada IHUŢ

ALTERNATIVE FEED SOURCES AND MILK QUALITY ENHANCEMENT

Roxana Elena (VASILIU) ŞTEFAN, Andreea Ionela ZINCA, Veronica Denisa LUNGU, Livia VIDU, Iuliana Ştefania (BOLOLOI) BORDEI, Viorica CONSTANTIN Monica Paula MARIN

COMPARATIVE RESEARCH ON THE INFLUENCE OF THE GROWTH SYSTEM AND NUTRITION OF LACTATING COWS ON THE QUALITY AND CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF MILK

Andreea Ionela ZINCA, Veronica Denisa LUNGU, Roxana Elena (VASILIU) ŞTEFAN, Iuliana Ştefania (BOLOLOI) BORDEI, Dumitru DRAGOTOIU

16:45 – 17:00 COFFEE BREAK

IDENTIFICATION AND ANALYSIS OF PROCESSING AND CONSUMPTION CHARACTERISTICS OF FISH IN RESTAURANTS IN BUCHAREST-ILFOV AREA

Cristian CRISTEA, Monica Paula MARIN, Gratiela BAHACIU, Elena Narcisa POGURSCHI, Ionela Florentina (ENACHE) TOMA, Gheorghe DOBROTĂ, Carmen Georgeta NICOLAE

SUSTAINABLE GROWTH POULTRY SYSTEMS AND MEAT QUALITY. A REVIEW

Veronica Denisa LUNGU, Andreea Ionela ZINCA, Roxana Elena (VASILIU) ȘTEFAN, Iuliana Ștefania (BOLOLOI) BORDEI, Dumitru DRAGOTOIU

RESEARCH ON THE INFLUENCE OF DILUTION MEDIA ON RAM SPERM CRYOPRESERVATION

Elena CIBOTARU, Grigore DARIE, Irina DJENJERA, Oleg CHISALITA, Iacob DOMNICA

THE ROAD TO BIOGLASS

Sara BOTEZAN, Răzvan ȘTEFAN, Daniel Severus DEZMIREAN

TOTAL PHENOLICS, TOTAL FLAVONOIDS AND ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY IN CHOKEBERRY, BLACKBERRY AND BLACKCURRANT LEAVES AND BERRIES DURING RIPENING STAGES

Camelia-Ioana IGNĂTESCU, Adriana Cristina URCAN, Adriana CRISTE

GREEN SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF BIOACTIVE PROPERTIES OF SILVER, GOLD, TITANIUM AND COPPER NANOPARTICLES MEDIATED BY EXTRACTS OF *SAMBUCUS L.*

Andrei-Lucian PAȘCA, Adriana CRISTE, Adriana Cristina URCAN

PALYNOLOGICAL ANALYSIS AND HEAVY METALS CHARACTERIZATION OF BEE POLLEN AND BEE SAMPLES FROM DIFFERENT ROMANIAN APIARIES

Claudia PAȘCA, Otilia BOBIȘ, Daniel Severus DEZMIREAN

AN OVERVIEW OF THE EFFECT OF PREBIOTICS, PROBIOTICS AND POSTBIOTICS ON INTERNAL HONEY BEE PARASITE *NOSEMA SPP.*

Cristina Gabriela MATHE, Tudor Nicolas TERNAR, Gianluca ALBANESE, Alexandru Ioan GIURGIU, Adriana Cristina URCAN, Claudia PAȘCA, Melinda Maria TÓFALVI, Massimo IORIZZO, Daniel Severus DEZMIREAN

Thursday, 26th September 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

**PLENARY SESSION – Faculty of Veterinary Medicine
INVITED SPEAKERS**

Hall: The Blue Amphitheater - Life Sciences Institute

15:00 – 16:30

Chairman: Prof. Alessandro SEGUINO, PhD

Moderators: Prof. Sanda ANDREI, PhD

Prof. Nicodim FIT, PhD

Secretary: Assis. Octavia TAMAS KRUMPE, PhD

INVITED SPEAKER

CONSERVATION PROGRAMME FOR NATIVE BREEDS: BRIEF SUMMARY ON ASPECTS TO CONSIDER WHEN ESTABLISHING IT IN THE SPANISH BREEDS "BERRENDO EN COLORADO" AND "BERRENDO EN NEGRO"

Miguel MORENO MILLAN, Evangelina RODERO SERRANO

EXPANDING THE FRONTIERS IN VETERINARY PUBLIC HEALTH EDUCATION: THE VIRTUAL SLAUGHTERHOUSE SIMULATOR

Alessandro SEGUINO

16:30 – 17:00 – COFFEE BREAK

Thursday, 26th September 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

Session 8: Veterinary Medicine - Clinical Sciences

Hall: The Blue Amphitheater - Life Sciences Institute

17:00 – 18:00 ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Chairman: Prof. Mihai CENARIU, PhD
Moderators: Assoc. Prof. Cosmin PESTEAN, PhD
Secretary: Assis. Cătălina MATEI LAȚIU, PhD

INFLUENCE OF *CRYPTOSPORIDIUM* SPP. INFECTION DIVERSITY ON WEIGHT GAIN IN LAMBS

Mariana LOURO, Zita RUANO, João LOZANO, Ioana MITREA, Isabel PEREIRA DA FONSECA, Jacinto GOMES

STARTING FROM SCRATCH AND SETTING UP THE DRUG PREPARATION LABORATORY MEANS QUALITY AND INDEPENDENCE

Ionuț Răzvan DOBRE, Iuliana IONAȘCU, Adriana-Daniela VLĂGIOIU

MOLECULAR GENETIC TECHNIQUES USED IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF *ENCEPHALITOOZON CUNICULI* IN DOMESTIC RABBITS (*ORYCTOLAGUS CUNICULUS*)

Anca-Alexandra DOBOȘI, Anamaria Ioana PAȘTIU, Dana Liana PUSTA

PREVALENCE OF ECHINOCOCCOSIS IN ANIMALS AND HUMANS IN ROMANIA (2007-2021): A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND META-ANALYSIS

Adriana GYÖRKE, Edina-Lenke HAIDU, Viorica MIRCEAN

Thursday, 27th September 2023

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

Session 10: Geodesy, Forestry and Applied Exact Sciences

Hall: The Green Amphitheater (ground floor), ICHAT building

15:00 - 18:30 ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Chairman: Mr. Nikola VUCIC, PhD
Moderator: Prof. Ciprian George FORA, PhD
Assoc. Prof. Horia Dan VLASIN, PhD
Secretary: Lect. Mircea NAP, PhD

FOR THE FIRST TIME IN THE USAMV-CN CAMPUS? A WEB APPLICATION THAT ASSIST IN THE IDENTIFICATION OF CLASSROOMS

Florica MATEI, Ioana POP, Tudor SĂLĂGEAN, Jutka DEAK, Elemer Emanuel ȘUBA, Lucia Adina TRUȚĂ, Cristian BUKOS, Cristian MĂLINAȘ

IMPLEMENTATION IN ARCGIS ONLINE OF A WATER NETWORK CONNECTION IN THE COMMUNE OF MITOCU DRAGOMIRNEI, SUCEAVA COUNTY

Cristian MĂLINAȘ, Ioana POP, Tudor SĂLĂGEAN, Anamaria MĂLINAȘ, Mircea NAP, Silvia CHIOREAN, Mihaela B. CRAȘOVAN, Florica MATEI

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS ON ECO-PRODUCTIVE TECHNOLOGIES FOR MODERN TIMBER HARVESTING IN CONTRAST WITH CLASSICAL ONES

Steluța-Maria ȘÎNGEORZAN, Ilie COVRIG, Mădălina COVRIG, Marius SÂNGEORZAN, Horia-Dan VLASIN

EVALUATION OF GEDI/ICESAT-2 SATELLITE LIDAR DATASETS POTENTIAL FOR GROUND SURFACE MODELLING

Mihnea CĂȚEANU, Sorina-Mihaela MICLESCU

THE EFFECT OF ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS ON THE GROWTH AND PRODUCTIVITY OF LINGONBERRY

Carla M. APARASCHIVE, Alina M. TRUȚĂ, Irina M. TODEA, Adriana F. SESTRĂȘ

UAV TECHNIQUES IN THE EARLY SIGNALING OF DISEASES IN FOREST NURSERIES

Mircea MOLDOVAN, Ioan TĂUT, Florin REBREAN

SALMONIDS PRODUCTIVITY ESTIMATION ON SOMEȘUL CALD RIVER, UPSTREAM OF IC PONOR, CLUJ COUNTY, ROMANIA

Horia-Dan VLASIN, Aldo-Bogdan CSAKI, Steluța-Maria ȘÎNGEORZAN

TOPO-BATHYMETRIC ANALYSIS FOR THE IDENTIFICATION OF OPTIMAL SECTIONS FOR THE DEPLOYMENT OF FLOATING STRUCTURES ON THE SOMEȘUL MARE RIVER

Adela – Maria NEAG, Cătălin-Ștefănel SABOU, Simion BRUMĂ, Florica MATEI, Tudor SĂLĂGEAN

NON-CHEMICAL METHODS FOR IMPROVING LARCH (*LARIX DECIDUA*) SEED GERMINATION

Petru TRUTA, Irina M. MORAR, Catalina DAN, Iulia ARION, Roxana L. STOIAN-DOD, Carla APARASCHIVE, Adriana F. SESTRAS, Alina M. TRUTA and Ioan-David LEONTIN

INFLUENCE OF ABIOTIC STRESS FACTORS ON THE GERMINATION OF SILVER FIR SEEDS FROM DIFFERENT ROMANIAN PROVENANCES

Irina M. MORAR, Alina M. TRUTA, Catalina DAN, Roxana L. STOIAN-DOD, Iulia ARION, Carla APARASCHIVE, Adriana F. SESTRAS

TRADITIONAL WOOD CONSTRUCTIONS SPECIFIC TO BUKOVINA, INTEGRATED INTO SILVOTOURISM

Alexandru COLIȘAR, Vasile ȘIMONCA, Mircea Ioan VARGA, Steluța-Maria SÎNGEORZAN, Vasile CEUCA, Horia Dan VLASIN, Oana ERHAN

Friday, 27th September, 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

Session 1 and 2: Agriculture and Environmental Protection

Hall A4, Rectorate Building

09:00 – 10:00 ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Chairman: Prof. Mignon SANDOR, PhD
Moderators: Prof. Florin PACURAR, PhD
Assoc. Prof. Loredana SUCIU, PhD

RESEARCHERS ON THE PRODUCTIVE PERFORMANCE OF SOME ROMANIAN PEA VARIETIES IN ECOLOGICAL AND CONVENTIONAL SYSTEMS

Cristina MOLDOVAN, Loredana SUCIU1, Anca PLEȘA, Anamaria MĂLINAȘ,
Roxana VIDICAN

EVALUATION OF THE MAIN PRODUCTION ELEMENTS OF THE VARIETY OF INDUSTRIAL HEMP (*CANNABIS SATIVA* L. VAR. *SATIVA*) MARA 21, UNDER THE CONDITIONS OF THE SUCEVAVA PLATEAU

Laurențiu PINTRIJEL, Costel SAMUIL, Constantin LUNGOCI, Iuliana MOTRESCU,
Ioan PUIU, Carmen Simona GHIȚĂU, Constantin Lucian HARAGA, Teodor ROBU

THE VARIABILITY OF YIELD AND QUALITY PERFORMANCE OF SOME WHEAT GENOTYPES IN DIFFERENT ECOLOGICAL CONDITIONS

Ionut RACZ, Rozalia KADAR, Diana HIRISCAU, Adina VARADI, Darius MORAR,
Simona Florina ISTICIOAIA, Beniamin ANDRAS, Indira GALIT, Gabriela GORINOIU

ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTS OF SLOW-RELEASE FERTILIZERS APPLICATION OVER THE DEVELOPMENT OF WINTER WHEAT UNDER CONTROLLED CLIMATE CONDITIONS

Lucian RĂUS, Diana BOLOHAN

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PLASMA TREATMENT TECHNOLOGIES ON SEED GERMINATION AND EARLY GROWTH OF *TRITICUM AESTIVUM* L. CV. GLOSA

Ioana-Cătălina NICOLAE, Oana VENAT, Roxana CICEOI, Bogdana MITU, Monica MAGUREANU

LIVING LAB APPROACH FOR BETTER UNDERSTANDING THE AGROFORESTRY SYSTEMS

Adrian GLIGA, Dumitrița DASCĂLU, Mignon ȘANDOR

POSTERS

AEP1. PHOTOSYNTHETIC EFFICIENCY AND METABOLIC CHANGES IN BRASSICACEAE PLANTS UNDER COMBINED DROUGHT AND OZONE STRESS

Flavia BORTES, Lucian COPOLOVICI, Cristian MOISA, Andreea LUPITU, Dana COPOLOVICI

AEP2. BIOCHAR FUNCTIONALISED WITH METAL OXIDES - POSSIBLE APPLICATIONS

Mariana BOCȘA, Adina STEGARESCU, Ildiko LUNG, Ocsana OPRIȘ, Maria-Loredana SORAN, Septimiu TRIPON, Irina KACSO, Madalina MILITARU, Alin CÂRDAN, Delia GLIGOR

AEP3. ASSESSMENT OF SURFACE WATER QUALITY ON UNIVERSITY AGRICULTURAL AND VETERINARY PROPERTIES: INSIGHTS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT

Abdelouahed FANNAKH, Nicodim Iosif FIT

AEP4. THE SELECTIVITY OF SOME HERBICIDES APPLIED IN PRE-EMERGENCE OF POTATO CV. ULTRA AND DARILENA IN THE SOUTH-EASTERN AREA OF TRANSYLVANIA

Manuela HERMEZIU, Lorena ADAM, Carmen CHELMEA

AEP5. THE INFLUENCE OF CROP ROTATION ON THE FAUNA OF PEST INSECTS IN THE CONDITIONS OF SOUTHERN ROMANIA

Maria IAMANDEI, Raluca Gabriela GEORGESCU, Madalina RĂDULEA, Ionuț Cristian POPA1, Luxița RĂȘNOVEANU

AEP6. RESEARCH ON THE EVALUATION OF QUANTITATIVE CHARACTERISTICS IN DRY BEANS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE IN CENTRAL MOLDAVIA, ROMANIA

Simona – Florina ISTICIOAIA, Alexandra LEONTE, Andreea – Sabina PINTILIE, Lorena - Diana POPA, Raluca REZI, Camelia URDĂ, Dumitru – Dorel BLAGA, Danela MURARIU, Gheorghe MATEI, Paula – Lucelia PINTILIE

AEP7. ANTIBIOTICS REMOVAL FROM WATER USING NEW ADSORBENT MATERIALS OBTAINED FROM FRUIT WASTES

Ildiko LUNG, Maria-Loredana SORAN, Ocsana OPRIȘ, Adina STEGARESCU1, József-Zsolt SZÜCS-BALÁZS, Ancuța BALLA, Stelian PINTEA

AEP8. THE EFFECT OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF STRESSES ON PLANT'S VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUND EMISSIONS

Andreea LUPITU, Lucian COPOLOVICI, Flavia BORTES, Maria COJOCARU-TOMA, Angelica OHINDOVSKI, Mihaela NARTEA, Cristian MOISA, Dana COPOLOVICI

AEP9. ANTIFUNGAL EFFECTS OF ESSENTIAL OILS ON PLANT PATHOGENS

Florentina-Veronica ONIȚA, Vasile FLORIAN

AEP10. LEAF AREA AND LENGTH ANALYSIS FOR RASPBERRY PROMIK BASED ON IMAGE PROCESSING TOOL

Alin Laviniu POPA, Ștefania GÂDEA, Valentina STOIAN, Sorin VÂTCĂ

AEP11. MANGANESSE DOPED ZINC OXIDE MODIFIED GRAPHITIC CARBON NITRIDE PHOTOCATALYS FOR ENVIRONMENTAL APPLICATION

Adriana POPA, Maria STEFAN, Ana VARADI, Cristian LEOSTEAN, Sergiu MACAVEI, Arpad ROSTAS, Ovidiu PANA, Dana TOLOMAN

AEP12. CERIUM DOPED ZINC OXIDE NANOFLOWERS AS ELECTROD MATERIAL FOR SUPERCAPACITORS

Adriana POPA, Dana TOLOMAN, Maria STEFAN, Arpad ROSTAS, Ameen AMMAR, Ana VARADI, Sergiu MACAVEI, Cristian LEOSTEAN, Emre ERDEM

AEP13. RESEARCH ON THE IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON THE CONTROLLED REPRODUCTION OF CULTURED FISH

Silvia RADU, Nicoleta Georgeta DOBROTĂ, Mioara COSTACHE, Daniela RADU, Gheorghe DOBROTĂ, Nino MARICA, Alin Constantin BARBU

AEP14. THE STUDY OF THE GALLOWAY BREED UNDER GRAZING CONDITIONS AT COJOCNA FARM

Mirela RANTA, Florin PĂCURAR, Ioana GHETE, Anamaria MĂLINAȘ

AEP15. EFFECTS OF RHIZOBACTERIA AND PHOSPHORUS SOURCES ON ROOT PHOSPHATASE ACTIVITY AND PHOSPHATES CONTENTS OF RHIZOSPHERE SOIL UNDER WATER STRESS

Vladimir ROTARU

AEP16. ECO-FRIENDLY SYNTHESIS OF ZNO-CAO NANOCOMPOSITES USING WASTE EGGSHELL

Manuela STAN, Alexandra CIORITA, Dan SILIPAS, Sergiu MACAVEI

AEP17. IMPACT OF LONG-TERM NITROGEN & PHOSPHORUS FERTILIZATIONS PRACTICES ON SOIL RESPIRATION POTENTIAL

Patrick URSAN, Alexandra GHEORGHITĂ, Driss TOUHAMI, Roxana VIDICAN

AEP18. DYNAMICS OF WOLF DISTRIBUTION IN THE CONTEXT OF ANTHROPOGENIC PRESSURE IN A PROTECTED AREA OF NORTHWESTERN ROMANIA

Bogdan VASILESCU, Mirela COMAN

AEP19. STUDIES ON ZINC-POTASSIUM SULFATE DOUBLE SALT, AS POTENTIAL COMPLEX FERTILIZER

Monica M. VENTER, Eszter E. TOASO, Liliana A. BIZO

AEP20. PERFORMANCE OF WINTER TRITICALE (TRITICOSECALE WITTM.) IN TRANSYLVANIAN PLAIN

Diana HIRIȘCĂU, Rozalia KADAR, Adina Varadi, Andreea-Sabina PINTILIE, Ionut RACZ

**AEP21. PERFORMANCE OF WINTER TRITICALE (TRITICOSECALE WITTM.) IN
TRANSYLVANIAN PLAIN**

Ionut RACZ

**13:00 –13:10 – Closing ceremony and Best Posters Awards – AULA MAGNA “Mihai
Serban”**

Friday, 27th September, 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

Session 3: Food Science and Technology

Hall A2, Rectorate Building

09:00 – 10:50 ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Chairperson: Assoc. Prof. Delia MICHIU, PhD
Moderator: Assoc. Prof. Andruța MUREȘAN, PhD
Secretary: Călina CIONT, PhD Student

**METABOLIC PROFILING OF PLANTS AS A TOOL FOR NEW BIOACTIVES
DISCOVERY AND QUALITY CONTROL**

Ludger A. WESSJOHANN

**FOODOMICS: EMERGING TECHNOLOGY TO INTEGRATE FOOD CHEMISTRY
IN THE SYSTEMS' BIOLOGY CONCEPT**

Carmen SOCACIU

**VALUE ADDED PROCESSES FOR CIRCULAR FOOD ECONOMY IN THE FRUIT
SECTOR**

Steliana RODINO

**ARGUMENTS FOR THE CONTINUITY OF MEAT PRODUCTION IN CONDITIONS
OF CLIMATE CHALLENGES**

Steliana RODINO, Rodica CHETROIU, Lidia IURCHEVICI

**FATS EXTRACTED FROM OIL PRESS CAKES, FISH MEAT, AND CHICKEN
HEARTS AS POTENTIAL COQ10 SUPPLEMENTS**

Cristina Anamaria SEMENIUC, Mara MANDRIOLI, Andersina Simina PODAR,
Floricuța RANGA, Maria Ioana SOCACIU, Simona Raluca IONESCU, Melinda
FOGARASI, Anca Corina FĂRCAȘ, Tullia Gallina TOSCHI, Dan Cristian
VODNAR, Sonia Ancuța SOCACI

**FROM ODORANTS TO OFF-FLAVOURS IN BEER: THE MAIN AROMA
COMPOUNDS AND STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVEMENT**

Corina Maria ȘUTEA, Elena MUDURA, Carmen Rodica POP, Eugen Dan RADU,
Paul Cristian CĂLUGĂR, Ioana DUMITRAȘCU, Teodora Emilia COLDEA

**PRELIMINARY STUDY ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF WAFFLE CONES
FORMULATED WITH POWDER FROM ROSEHIP WASTE**

Alexandra Raluca BORȘA (BOGDAN), Raluca Alexandra MATEI, Adriana
PĂUCEAN, Melinda FOGARASI, Andrei BORȘA, Maria Simona CHIȘ, Cristina
Anamaria SEMENIUC

FERMENTED BEVERAGES WITH FUNCTIONAL POTENTIAL: EXPLORING THE POSSIBLE USE OF GRAPE AND APPLE POMACE IN BEERS

Corina Maria ŞUTEA, Elena MUDURA, Carmen Rodica POP, Eugen Dan RADU, Paul Cristian CĂLUGĂR, Ioana DUMITRAŞCU, Teodora Emilia COLDEA

QUALITY AND AUTHENTICITY OF SAFFRON AND SENSORY ASPECTS

Maria Jenica URS, Mara MANDRIOLI, Cristina Anamaria SEMENIUC, Tullia Gallina TOSCHI

11:00 – 12:30 POSTER SESSION (PRESENTATION AND EVALUATION)

POSTERS

FST 1. COMPOSITION AND SENSORY ANALYSIS FOR QUALITY EVALUATION SMOKED CHEESE: INFLUENCE OF RIPENING PERIOD

Anamaria BOLBOS, Crina Carmen MUREŞAN, Romina MARC, Mădălina Oana MARINCAŞ

FST 2. ENSURING THE INNOCUITY OF RAW MILK THROUGH FRAUD DETECTION

Cristina-Maria CANJA, Alina MAIER, Geronimo Răducu BRĂNESCU, Mirabela Ioana LUPU

FST 3. LACTOBACILLUS PLANTARUM ADAPTABILITY ON SWEET POTATO SUBSTRATES

Cristina CHIOREAN, Adriana PĂUCEAN, Carmen POP, Rodica SIMA, Alexandru APAHIDEAN, Simona CHIŞ

FST 4. PROBIOTICS ENHANCE IRON OXIDE NANOPARTICLE ABSORPTION

Călina CIONT, Raluca Maria POP, Alexandru-Flaviu TĂBĂRAN, Lucian Barbu-TUDORAN, Ramona SUHAROSCHI, Dan Cristian VODNAR, Oana Lelia POP

FST 5. SENSORY, PHISICOCHEMICAL AND RHEOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF WHITE BREAD FORTIFICATION WITH A COMERCIAL MIXTURE OF VITAMINS AND MINERALS

Carmen-Alexandra CIRICAN, Claudia-Felicia OGNEAN, Mihai OGNEAN

FST 6. ROMANIAN CONSUMERS PERCEPTIONS, KNOWLEDGE AND EXPECTATIONS OF PSYCHOBOTICS AND THEIR POTENTIAL IMPACT ON MENTAL HEALTH

Ana-Maria COCEAN, Lavinia CĂLINOIU, Călina CIONT, Adrian MARTĂU, Bernadette TELEKY, Laura MITREA, Bianca ŞTEFĂNESCU, Amalia NEMEŞ, Diana PLĂMADĂ, Anita VARVARA, Răzvan ODOCHEANU, Dan VODNAR

FST 7. WINEMAKING METHODS AND TASTING CONTEXT IN CORRELATION WITH SENSORIAL SENSES AND PHYSICOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS

George Ștefan COMAN, Camelia Elena LUCHIAN, Elena Cristina SCUTARAȘU, Lucia Cintia COLIBABA, Valeriu COTEA

FST 8. FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF EGG YOLKS: THEIR NUTRITIONAL VALUE AND HEALTH IMPLICATION

Florina-Dorina COVACIU, Gabriela CRISTEA, Veronica FLOARE-AVRAM, Ioana FEHER

FST 9. WHERE DO THE POTATOES ON THE PLATE COME FROM?

Gabriela CRISTEA, Cezara VOICA, Ioana FEHER, Romulus PUSCAS, Dana Alina MAGDAS

FST 10. DISTILLERY BY-PRODUCTS FERMENTATION WITH LACTOBACILLUS PLANTARUM STRAIN

Gina-Maria CUCUIET, Adriana PĂUCEAN, Simona MAN, Carmen Rodica POP, Maria-Simona CHIȘ

FST 11. INVESTIGATION OF THE PHENOLIC PROFILE AND ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF *ACHILLEA MILLEFOLIUM* L. AND *CALENDULA OFFICINALIS* L.

Teodora DAN, Katalin SZABO, Sanda ANDREI

FST 12. APPLICATION OF HEALTH RISK INDICES TO ASSESS HEAVY METALS CONTAMINATION IN EGG AND PORK MEAT

Adriana DEHELEAN, Gabriela CRISTEA, Romulus PUSCAS, Dana-Alina MAGDAS

FST 13. SYNTHESIS, PURITY ASSESSMENT AND ANALYTICAL DETERMINATION OF THIOSULFINATES FROM PLANT-BASED SAMPLES

Teodor-Sebastian DOROFTEI, Bogdan Marius BOȘCA, Augustin-Cătălin MOȚ

FST 14. WILD MUSHROOMS EVALUATION THROUGH ELEMENTAL PROFILE FOLLOWED BY ADVANCED CHEMOMETRIC APPROACH

Ioana FEHER, Adriana DEHELEAN, Gabriela CRISTEA, Veronica FLOARE AVRAM, Florina COVACIU, Romulus PUSCAS, Dana-Alina MAGDAS

FST 15. ASSESSMENT OF BISPHENOL A AND HEAVY METALS LEVELS IN COMMERCIAL FRUIT JUICES

Veronica FLOARE-AVRAM, Adriana DEHELEAN, Ioana FEHER, Florina COVACIU, Dana-Alina MAGDAS

FST 16. INTEGRATED BIOREFINERY FOR RECOVERING VALUABLE BIOMOLECULES FROM FOOD PROCESSING BY-PRODUCTS

Darleen GENUTTIS, Ann-Kristin GÄRTNER, Sarah ENGELHARDT, Alexandru RUSU

FST 17. FROM NICHE TO MAINSTREAM – ALTERNATIVE PROTEINS FOR EVERYBODY AND EVERYWHERE

Darleen GENUTTIS, Ann-Kristin GÄRTNER, Sarah ENGELHARDT, Alexandru RUSU

FST 18. ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF THERMAL TREATMENT ON BEECHNUT (*FAGUS SYLVATICA* L.) OILS

Alexandra Raluca LAZĂR, Andreea PUȘCAȘ, Anda Elena TANISLAV, Vlad MUREȘAN

FST 19. A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF HONEY QUALITY BETWEEN COMMERCIAL AND LOCAL PRODUCERS

Mirabela Ioana LUPU, Cristina Maria CANJA, Alina MAIER, Vasile PĂDUREANU

FST 20. AN OVERVIEW OF PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND SENSORY EVALUATION OF CHICKEN LIVER PATÉ FORMULATIONS

Alina MAIER, Mirabela Ioana LUPU, Cristina Maria CANJA, Sorina Denisa UNGUREANU, Vasile PĂDUREANU

FST 21. EDIBLE INSECTS - PAST, PRESENT & FUTURE, REVIEW

Arnilva MARA, Diana DRAGAN, Horia BUNESCU, Vasile FLORIAN, Teodora FLORIAN

FST 22. IDENTIFY STRATEGIC CAPABILITIES IN A HALVA PRODUCING FACTORY BY MODELING AND SIMULATION WITH PETRI NETS

Ion Dan MIRONESCU, Ilie BÎRSAN, Monica MIRONESCU

FST 23. SUPERIOR USE OF RESIDUES TO ENLARGE THE RANGE OF FOOD PRODUCTS

Monica MIRONESCU, Roxana-Elena DOSPINA, Alexandra-Monica STANCIU, Cornelia DOȘTEȚAN-ABĂLARU

FST 24. GRAPHENE PRODUCED VIA ELECTROCHEMICAL EXFOLIATION IN INSTANT COFFEE AS EFFECTIVE SENSING MATERIAL FOR TRACE DETECTION OF SULFAMETHAZINE

Lidia MĂGERUȘAN, Florina POGĂCEAN, Stela PRUNEANU, Florina-Dorina COVACIU

FST 25. ENHANCED SERS DETECTION OF THIABENDAZOLE IN BENTONITE-FILTERED FROZEN BLUEBERRY EXTRACTS

Csilla MOLNÁR, Camelia BERGHIAN-GROȘAN, Dana Alina MĂGDAȘ, Gabriela CRISTEA, Adriana DEHELEAN, Simona CÎNȚĂ PÎNZARU

FST 26. DEVELOPMENT OF A QuEChERS METHOD FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF 4 EU PRIORITY POLYCYCLIC AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS BY GC-MS/MS FROM CEREALS

Mioara NEGOIȚĂ, Adriana Laura MIHAI, Alina Cristina ADASCĂLULUI, Laurențiu Mihai PALADE

FST 27. ANTIMICROBIAL ACTION MECHANISM AND TOXICOLOGICAL PROFILE OF SOME LAMIACEAE ESSENTIAL OILS AND THEIR CONSTITUENTS

Alina L. NISTOR, Carmen R. POP, Giorgiana M. CĂTUNESCU, Laura COȚ, Ancuța M. ROTAR

FST 28. APPLICATIONS OF MESPILUS GERMANICA L. (MEDLAR) IN THE FOOD INDUSTRY

Doru Ion NISTOR, Romina Alina MARC, Crina Carmen MUREȘAN

FST 29. RESEARCHES REGARDING OBTAINING BISCUITS WITH IMPROVED NUTRITIONAL CHARACTERISTICS

Vasilica OPRESCU, Claudia-Felicia OGNEAN, Mihai OGNEAN

FST 30. EXPLOITATION OF ALFALFA SPROUTS AND SEEDS FOR OBTAINING SOURDOUGH BREAD WITH ENHANCED NUTRITIONAL QUALITY

Delia-Elena PĂUȘAN, Simona MAN, Simona-Maria CHIȘ, Carmen Rodica POP, Anamaria POP, Vlad MUREȘAN, Andreea PUȘCAȘ, Floricuța RANGA, Ersilia ALEXA, Anca-Corina FĂRCAȘ, Adriana PĂUCEAN

FST 31. ANTIBACTERIAL POTENTIAL OF A BACTERIAL CELLULOSE-BASED PACKAGING MATERIAL ENRICHED WITH MENTHA PIPERITA EXTRACT

Anna PÉTER, Ioana M. BODEA, Bianca POPESCU, Dénes-Szilvester MODI, Sorin STĂNILĂ, Piotr KOCZOŃ, Joanna BRYŚ, Carmen POP, Giorgiana CĂTUNESCU, Ancuța M. ROTAR

FST 32. ADVANCED BIO-BASED MATERIALS AND PRODUCTS FROM CIRCULAR USES OF SOYBEAN BYPRODUCTS AND WASTE

Steliana RODINO, Alina BUTU, Marian BUTU

FST 33. INFLUENCE OF LEUCONOSTOC CITREUM DSM 5577 SOURDOUGH ON SUGAR-FREE MUFFINS QUALITY

Maria-Florina ROȘCA, Simona Maria MAN, Maria Simona CHIȘ, Carmen R. POP, Andreea PUȘCAȘ, Laura STAN, Anca C. FĂRCAȘ, Florica RANGA, Anda TANISLAV, Adriana PĂUCEAN

FST 34. FROM FLOWER TO FUNCTION: THE BENEFITS OF POLLEN PROTEIN AND FERMENTATION– AN OVERVIEW

Roxana Anca SĂLĂGEAN, RAMONA SUHAROSCHI

FST 35. A REVIEW OF THE CYTOTOXIC PROPERTIES OF *SORBUS AUCUPARIA* L.

Giorgiana A. SPALLER, Romina A. MARC, Crina C. MUREȘAN

FST 36. OPTIMIZING THE COMPOSITION OF RED WINES OBTAINED FROM FETEASCĂ NEAGRĂ GRAPES BY REVERSE OSMOSIS

Alexandru Gabriel SUDUC, Cătălin Ioan ZAMFIR, Camelia Elena LUCHIAN, Lucia Cintia COLIBABA, Andreea ȚURCANU, Răzvan George NIȚĂ, Valeriu V. COTEA

FST 37. ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES OF ICARISIDE II COMPLEXES

Róbert SZABÓ, Csaba PÁL RÁCZ, Vasile Francisc DULF

FST 38. ENHANCING ITACONIC ACID PRODUCTION FROM AGRO-INDUSTRIAL WASTE: ENZYME-DRIVEN BIOSYNTHESIS STRATEGIES

Bernadette TELEKY, Laura MITREA, Amalia NEMEȘ, Diana PLĂMADĂ, Mihaela PĂȘCUȚĂ, Lavinia CĂLINOIU, Anita VARVARA, Bianca ȘTEFĂNESCU, Ana-Maria COCEAN, Adrian MARTĂU, Elemer SIMON, Paula PLOSCA, Răzvan ODOCHEANU, Dan VODNAR

FST 39. DEVELOPMENT OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL RHENIUM AND IRIIDIUM FLAVONOID COMPLEXES AS NOVEL METALLODRUGS AND CATALYSTS FOR ENHANCED ANTICANCER THERAPY

Monica TRIF, Jörg SCHACHNER, Hristina HRISTOVA, Maria João G. FERREIRA, Cláudia Alexandra Carica Figueira, Ljiljana MIHAJLOVIĆ-LALIĆ, Milan MILOVANOVIĆ, Stefan NIKOLIĆ

FST 40. UNLOCKING THE POWER OF LUPINE: A SUSTAINABLE PROTEIN SOURCE FOR FUTURE FOODS

Alexandru RUSU, Ann-Kristin GÄRTNER, Malte BETHKE, Darleen GENUTTIS, Sarah ENGELHARDT, Monica TRIF

FST 41. PARTIAL SUBSTITUTION OF PORK FAT WITH BEESWAX OLEOGELS FOR IMPROVING THE NUTRITIONAL VALUE OF DRY FERMENTED SAUSAGES

Simona PERȚA-CRIȘAN, Florentina-Daniela MUNTEANU, Iolanda TOLAN, Bianca-Denisa CHEREJI, Dumitru CONDRAT, Lucian COPOLOVICI, Claudiu-Ștefan URSACHI

FST 42. INVESTIGATING THE MECHANISM OF MAGNESIUM UPTAKE IN *LACTOBACILLUS RHAMNOSUS*

Rodica-Anita VARVARA, Ana-Maria COCEAN, Lavinia CĂLINOIU, Călina CIONT, Adrian MARTĂU, Bernadette TELEKY, Laura MITREA, Bianca ȘTEFĂNESCU, Amalia NEMEȘ, Diana PLĂMADĂ, Răzvan ODOCHEANU, Heike BUDDE, Ruth LEY, Dan VODNAR

FST 43. ASSESSMENT OF ELEMENTAL DETERMINATION OF EGG-SHELL

Cezara VOICA, Gabriela CRISTEA, Ioana FEHER

FST 44. ASSESSMENT OF ELEMENTAL DETERMINATION OF SPRING WATERS

Cezara VOICA, Gabriela CRISTEA

FST 45. AN OVERVIEW OF THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND BIOACTIVITIES OF *VETIVERIA ZIZANIOIDES* (L.) NASH ESSENTIAL OIL

Andreea DAVID, Anca FĂRCAȘ, Sonia Ancuța SOCACI

13:00 –13:10 – Closing ceremony and Best Posters Awards – AULA MAGNA “Mihai Serban”

Friday, 27th September, 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

Session 4: Horticulture

Hall: ICHAT building – 3rd Floor Lobby

09:30-12:30 – POSTER SESSION (PRESENTATION AND EVALUATION)

Chairman: Assoc. Prof. Catalina DAN, PhD
Moderators: Assoc. Prof. Denisa JUCAN, PhD
Lect. Sonia BODEA, PhD
Secretary: Lect. Andreea ANDRECAN, PhD

FHADR1. DEVELOPMENT OF NOVEL FOOD PRODUCTS BASED ON QUINOA

Eftychios APOSTOLIDIS, Panteleimon STAVROPOULOS, Antonios Mavroeidis, Ioanna MANDALA, Dimitrios BILALIS, Ioanna KAKABOUKI

FHADR2. ON THE WAY OF IDENTIFYING *METHYLOBACTERIUM* SPECIES SYMBIOTIC TO SUNFLOWER

Adriana AURORI, Rodica POP, Cristian Radu SISEA

FHADR3. DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC HETEROGENEOUS MATERIALS IN SALAD TOMATOES: PRELIMINARY PHASES OF EVALUATION BASED ON YIELD AND QUALITY OF STARTING POPULATIONS

Adrián BERENGUER-GARCÍA, David HERNÁNDEZ-MESEGUER, Marisa JIMÉNEZ-PÉREZ, Ana M. ADALID-MARTÍNEZ, Ana FITA, Adrián RODRÍGUEZ-BURRUEZO

FHADR4. COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SPANISH TOMATO HEIRLOOMS UNDER ORGANIC FARMING IN THE MEDITERRANEAN COAST OF SPAIN

Adrián BERENGUER-GARCÍA, Marisa JIMÉNEZ-PÉREZ, David HERNÁNDEZ-MESEGUER, María PALLARDO-MARAVILLA, Ana ADALID-MARTÍNEZ, Ana FITA, Adrián RODRÍGUEZ-BURRUEZO

FHADR5. HISTORICAL AND LANDSCAPE STUDY - STRĂOANE, VRANCEA COUNTY

Păunița BOANCĂ, Dan Florin FLORUȚ, Sonia BODEA, Alice OPRICĂ, Adelina DUMITRAȘ, Andrei MĂRINCEAN

FHADR6. LANDSCAPE AND VISUAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT. CASE STUDY: SĂȘAR NEIGHBORHOOD, BAIA MARE

Păunița BOANCĂ, Dan Florin FLORUȚ, Sonia BODEA, Alice OPRICĂ, Adelina DUMITRAȘ, Andrei MĂRINCEAN

FHADR7. BIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES AND FRUIT QUALITY TRAITS OF THREE SWEET CHERRY VARIETIES GROWN IN THE EXPERIMENTAL ORCHARD OF UASVM CLUJ-NAPOCA

Orsolya BORSAL, Lehel LUKÁCS, Sandor RÓZSA, Olimpia-Alina IORDĂNESCU, Ionuț Dascălu, Viorel MITRE, Cătălina DAN, Flavia-Andreea ANDRECAN

FHADR8. THE INFLUENCE OF *MYCORRHIZAE* ON GRAPE QUALITY AND BIOLOGICAL INDICES OF VEGETATIVE BALANCE IN BURGUND MARE VARIETY, IN THE CLIMATE CONDITIONS OF SATU-MARE

Anamaria CĂLUGĂR, Zsolt-Tibor GAL, Florin-Dumitru BORA, Anca Cristina BABEȘ, Cladiu Ioan BUNEA

FHADR9. EFFECTS OF *IN VITRO* CULTURE PERIOD AND PLANT GROWTH REGULATORS ON BIOMASS PRODUCTION IN SEVEN *HYPERICUM* SPECIES

Doina CLAPA, Monica HÂRȚA, Ana Maria RADOMIR, Adrian George PETICILĂ, Mirela Irina CORDEA, Adelina DUMITRAȘ, Dorin Ioan SUMEDREA

FHADR10. STUDIES ON WINES OBTAINED IN DIFFERENT CLIMATIC YEARS FROM FETEASCA NEAGRA GRAPE VARIETY IN COTESTI VINEYARD

Lucia Cintia COLIBABA, Daniel-Alexandru HRISCU, Camelia Elena LUCHIAN, Daniela SIMINEL, Valeriu V. COTEA

FHADR11. WINEMAKING METHODS AND TASTING CONTEXT IN CORRELATION WITH SENSORIAL SENSES AND PHYSICOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS

George Ștefan COMAN, Camelia Elena LUCHIAN, Elena Cristina SCUTARAȘU, Lucia Cintia COLIBABA, Valeriu COTEA

FHADR12. ASSESSMENT OF TOMATOES GENOTYPES IN GREENHOUSE CONDITIONS

Mirela Irina CORDEA, Ioana MOLDOVAN, Monica HARTA, Doina CLAPA, Ulian BESLEAGA, Lehel LUKACS

FHADR13. PHENOTYPIC PROFILES FOR CHERRY VARIETIES ESTABLISHED AT UASVM CLUJ-NAPOCA

Catalina DAN, Adriana SESTRAS, Flavia-Andreea ANDRECAN, Orsolya BORSAL, Alina TRUTA, Irina MORAR, Mădălina MILITARU, Radu E. SESTRAS

FHADR14. ALMOND CULTIVARS RELEASED AT RESEARCH STATION FOR FRUIT GROWING CONSTANȚA

Corina GAVĂT, Mihaela NISTOR

FHADR15. THE EFFECT OF BLANCHING, COATING AND DRYING METHOD ON THE QUALITY OF DEHYDRATED APPLE SLICES

Tincuța-Marta GOCAN, Orsolya BORSAL, Daniela-Sabina POȘTA, Iuliana MOTRESCU, Lehel LUKÁCS, Sándor RÓZSA

FHADR16. THE INFLUENCE OF HYBRID AND PLANTING DENSITY ON KOHLRABI YIELD

Tincuța-Marta GOCAN, Rodica Maria SIMA, Mariana-Florica BEI, Sándor RÓZSA, Gheorghe POȘTA, Alexandru-Ioan APAHIDEAN

FHADR17. *CHRYSANTHEMUM* MICROPROPAGATION – THE HIGHLIGHTS OF 30 YEARS OF RESEARCH IN SERBIA

Sladjana JEVREMOVIC, Milana TRIFUNOVIC-MOMCILOV, Angelina SUBOTIC

FHADR18. EVALUATION OF *CAPSICUM* PEPPER LANDRACES UNDER SUSTAINABLE FARMING AND DEFICITARY IRRIGATION: YIELD, FRUIT WEIGHT AND CAROTENOIDS

Marisa JIMÉNEZ-PÉREZ, Roberto JUAN-MÉNDEZ, Adrián BERENGUER-GARCÍA, Mireia ROMANS-ESCRIVÁ, Estela MORENO-PERIS, Ana FITA, María D. RAIGÓN, Adrián RODRÍGUEZ-BURRUEZO

FHADR19. TOWARDS MORE RESILIENT PRODUCTION OF *CAPSICUM* PEPPERS: DEVELOPING ORGANIC HETEROGENEOUS MATERIALS BASED ON COMPOSITE CROSS POPULATIONS-INITIAL STAGES

Marisa JIMÉNEZ-PÉREZ, Roberto JUAN-MÉNDEZ, Adrián BERENGUER-GARCÍA, Estela MORENO-PERIS, Ana FITA, Adrián RODRÍGUEZ-BURRUEZO

FHADR20. EFFECT OF SALINITY AND PLANT GROWTH PROMOTING MICROORGANISMS (PGPMs) ON THE PERFORMANCE OF CHIA (*SALVIA HISPANICA* L.)

Ioanna KAKABOUKI, Panteleimon STAVROPOULOS, Antonios MAVROEIDIS, Antigoni-Eleni FOLINA, Ioannis ROUSSIS, Dimitrios BILALIS

FHADR21. EFFECT OF SUBSTRATE ON MICROGREENS PRODUCTION

Ioanna KAKABOUKI, Panteleimon STAVROPOULOS, Antonios MAVROEIDIS, Spyridon KOUREMPES, Maria-Christina KOUREMPE, Ioannis ROUSSIS, Sotiria PATSIALI, Konstantinos PANTALEON

FHADR22. THE EFFECT OF THINNING ON PEACH IN SOUTH-EAST ROMANIA

Gheorghe LĂMUREANU

FHADR23. EFFECTS OF HEAT STRESS ON THE MEDITERRANEAN ENDEMIC HALOPHYTE *LIMONIUM GIRARDIANUM*

Diana MIRCEA, Clara SANCHIS, Isabel MARTÍNEZ NIETO, Pilar SORIANO, Monica BOSCAIU

FHADR24. USE OF SYNTHETIC SEED TECHNOLOGY FOR THE REGROWTH OF ENCAPSULATED EXPLANTS IN *FRAGARIA* × *ANANASSA* USING PHYTOHORMONES AND ACTIVATED CHARCOAL

Ioana-Cătălina NICOLAE, Oana VENAT, Adrian George PETICILĂ, Dorel HOZA

FHADR25. THE EFFECT OF EXPLANT TYPE AND GROWTH REGULATORS ON CALLUS INDUCTION IN *PASSIFLORA QUADRANGULARIS*

Paula OROS, Corina CĂTANĂ, Maria CANTOR

FHADR26. THE INFLUENCE OF GENOTYPE AND CULTURE MEDIUM ON *IN VITRO* PROLIFERATION IN *HEUCHERA* SPP.

Paula OROS, Corina CĂTANĂ, Cristian Cătălin CIOBANU

FHADR27. THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE PARASITE *ENCARSIA FORMOSA* GAHAN IN COMBATING THE WHITEFLY *TRIALEURODES VAPORARIORUM*

Daniel POPA, Ioan-Lion CHIPER, Lidia CHIPER, Laura-Mirabela MĂRGINEAN

FHADR28. PRELIMINARY STUDY ON THE INFLUENCE OF POTTING SOIL ON *MAGNOLIA GRANDIFLORA* L. SEED GERMINATION AND PLANT GROWTH

Daniela Sabina POȘTA, Giancarla VELICEVICI, Ioana Mihaela MĂLĂESCU, Marius SILIVĂȘAN, Veronica SĂRĂȚEANU, Tincuța-Marta GOCAN, Orsolya BORSAL, Sandor RÓZSA, Ilie-Cosmin CÂNTAR, Roberto Renato BERNARDIS

FHADR29. ROMANIAN GENETIC RESOURCES OF CUCUMBERS - PERSPECTIVES AND CHALLENGES IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL WARMING

Ionela Filona RĂDUCU, Aurora DOBRIN, Liliana BĂDULESCU, Elena Maria DRĂGHICI

FHADR30. POST-HARVEST QUALITY MAINTENANCE IN TWO LOCAL TOMATO POPULATIONS FROM CLUJ COUNTY

Sandor ROZSA, Gheorghe POȘTA, Alexandru-Ioan APAHIDEAN, Lehel LUKACS, Tincuța-Marta GOCAN, Ileana ANDREICA, Ioana MOLDOVAN

FHADR31. EFFECT OF THE FRUIT PHENOLOGICAL STAGE ON GERMINATION OF *CAPSICUM* PEPPERS. WAX PEPPER AS A CASE OF STUDY

Eva M. SOLBES-GARCÍA, Ana DE LUIS-MARGARIT, Ana FITA, Adrián RODRÍGUEZ-BURRUEZO

FHADR32. STUDY OF THE AGE OF SEEDS ON GERMINATION IN VEGETABLES. *CAPSICUM* PEPPERS AS AN EXAMPLE

Eva M. SOLBES-GARCÍA, Ana DE LUIS-MARGARIT, Mónica BOSCAIU, Adrián RODRÍGUEZ-BURRUEZO

FHADR33. OPTIMIZING THE COMPOSITION OF RED WINES OBTAINED FROM FETEASCĂ NEAGRĂ GRAPES BY REVERSE OSMOSIS

Alexandru Gabriel SUDUC, Cătălin Ioan ZAMFIR, Camelia Elena LUCHIAN, Lucia Cintia COLIBABA, Tiberiu ANDRIEȘ, Andreea ȚURCANU, Răzvan George NIȚĂ, Valeriu V. COTEA

FHADR34. RESEARCH ON THE USE OF ENZYMATIC PREPARATIONS FOR THE PROTEIN STABILIZATION OF WINES OBTAINED FROM BUSUIOACA DE BOHOTIN

Andreea TURCANU, Lucia Cintia COLIBABA, Camelia LUCHIAN, Marius NICULAUA, Catalin ZAMFIR, Valeriu V. COTEA

FHADR35. WATER MANAGEMENT SUSTAINABLE SOLUTION, CASE STUDY FOR A NEW RESIDENTIAL AREA IN CLUJ-NAPOCA

Alida VIȘAN, Denisa JUCAN

11-12:30, Workshop: COST Action 21134, Towards Zero Pesticide Agriculture: The European Network for Sustainability

13:30-15:30, Workshop: AKIS G4AE, Economically Sustainable Grazing by Respecting the Environment and Biodiversity

15:30-16:30, Workshop: Connecting and Mobilizing the EU Agricultural Advisory Community to Support the Transition to Climate Smart Farming. The ClimateSmartAdvisors project

13:00 –13:10 – Closing ceremony and Best Posters Awards – AULA MAGNA “Mihai Serban”

Friday, 27th September, 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

Session 5: Economics and Rural Development

Hall: Library – 1st Floor, ICHAT

09:00 – 12:30 – ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Chairman: Prof. Felix ARION, PhD
Moderator: Prof. Diana DUMITRAS, PhD
Lect. Andra PORUTIU, PhD

**THE IMPACT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF NON-AGRICULTURAL ACTIVITIES
ON THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ROMANIAN RURAL SPACE**

Tabita ADAMOV, Tiberiu IANCU, Gabriela POPESCU, Ramona CIOLAC, Dragoş
CHENDE, Marius GORDAN

**RURAL DEVELOPMENT IN ROMANIA: EVOLUTION AND TRENDS OF THE
SMART VILLAGE CONCEPT**

Mihaela PILA

**REVEALING THE CHANNELS OF INFORMATION TAILORED TO THE NEEDS OF
ROMANIAN GRAZING FARMERS**

Ionel Mugurel JITEA, Diana E. DUMITRAŞ

**FOUNDATION OF AN AGRICULTURAL COOPERATIVE FOR PROCESSING
VEGETABLES AND FRUITS IN THE RURAL AREA OF ROMANIA**

Călin VAC, Maria VAC, Marius SABĂU, Lucica ARMANCA, Ileana ANDREICA

**TRANSFĂGĂRĂŞAN: FROM STRATEGIC MILITARY ROAD, FACILITATOR OF
TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN FĂGĂRAŞ MOUNTAINS**

Vasile Mihai CUCERZAN

**DRIVERS TO SUPPORT THE TRANSITION TO CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE
IN ROMANIA**

Valentin C. MIHAI, Iulia S. DAN, Ionel M. JITEA, Diana E. DUMITRAŞ, Mihaela
MIHAI, Răzvan POPA Cătălin DRAGOMIR

11-12:30, Workshop: COST Action 21134, Towards Zero Pesticide Agriculture: The European Network for Sustainability

13:30-15:30, Workshop: AKIS G4AE, Economically Sustainable Grazing by Respecting the Environment and Biodiversity

15:30-16:30, Workshop: Connecting and Mobilizing the EU Agricultural Advisory Community to Support the Transition to Climate Smart Farming. The ClimateSmartAdvisors project

13:00 –13:10 – Closing ceremony and Best Posters Awards – AULA MAGNA “Mihai Serban”

Friday, 27th September, 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

Session 6 and 7: Animal Science and Biotechnologies

Hall: Red Amphitheater, Library Building

09:00 – 12:00 POSTER SESSION (PRESENTATION AND EVALUATION)

Chairman: Lect. Mihai Şuteu, PhD
Moderator: Lect. Claudia Paşca, PhD
Secretary: Assist. Alexandru Deac, PhD

ASB1. COMPARATIVE RESEARCH ON BREEDING VALUE PREDICTION FOR CALVING SCORE IN BEEF BREED CATTLE

Rodica Stefania PELMUS, Mircea Catalin ROTAR, Mihail Alexandru GRAS, Cristina VAN

ASB2. OVERVIEW ON STRATEGIES TO REDUCE THE CARBON FOOTPRINT IN DAIRY CATTLE FARMS

Marinela ENCULESCU, Ioana NICOLAE, Madalina MINCU

ASB3. INFLUENCE OF GENOTYPE AND SEX ON BODY WEIGHT EVOLUTION OF LAMBS

Cristian Vasile ILISIU, Elena ILISIU, Daniela Rodica MARE, Andreea - Hortensa ANGHEL, Vasile - Calin ILISIU, Dorina NADOLU, Krisztina Pál CHIOREAN

ASB4. RESEARCHERS ON THE INFLUENCE OF SUCKLING PERIOD OF KIDS ON PRODUCTIVE EFFICIENCY IN SAANEN GOATS

Dorina NADOLU, Zoia Camelia ZAMFIR, Andreea Hortanse ANGHEL, Laura MARINICA, Cristian Vasile ILIŞIU, Elena ILIŞIU

ASB5. RESEARCH ON THE EVOLUTION OF MILK PRODUCTION IN ANGLO-NUBIAN PRIMIPAROUS GOATS ACCORDING TO THE AGE OF THE FIRST MATING

Laura MARINICA, Dorina NADOLU, Andreea Hortanse ANGHEL, Alexandru Gabriel VARTIC, Constantin PASCAL

ASB6. MEASUREMENTS OF LAYING HENS' BEHAVIORAL ADAPTATION IN THERMAL STRESS

Gabriela Maria CORNESCU, Tatiana Dumitra PANAITTE, Ana Elena CISMILEANU

ASB7. EFFECT OF *ULVA LACTUCA* AS A FEED ADDITIVE ON GROWTH PERFORMANCE AND OXIDATIVE STRESS ON *ACIPENSER STELLATUS* AND *ACIPENSER RUTHENUS*

Alina Nicoleta MACOVEIU, Mirela CREŢU, Maria Desimira STROE, Angelica DOCAN, Floricel Maricel DIMA, Lorena DEDIU

ASB 8. FISH BIODIVERSITY AND STOCK ASSESSMENT IN THE DANUBE RIVER: INSIGHTS FROM KM 166-175

Angelica DOBRE, Maria Desimira STROE, Mirela CREȚU, Marilena Florentina LĂCĂTUȘ, Floricel Maricel DIMA

ASB9. ANALYZING THE IMPACTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON THE HYDROLOGICAL REGIME AND AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY OF THE DANUBE RIVER

Desimira Maria STROE, Angelica DOBRE, Mirela CRETU, Magdalena TENCIU, Elena Ioana COMAN, Neculai PATRICHE

ASB10. RESEARCH ON THE IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON THE CONTROLLED REPRODUCTION OF CULTURED FISH

Silvia RADU, Nicoleta Georgeta DOBROTĂ, Mioara COSTACHE, Daniela RADU, Gheorghe DOBROTĂ, Nino MARICA, Alin Constantin BARBU

ASB11. SEASONAL VARIATIONS IN THE PREVALENCE OF ECTOPARASITIC INFESTATION IN CIPRINID FRY FROM FISH FARM

Daniela RADU, Mioara COSTACHE, Nino MARICA, Alin BARBU, Carmen Georgeta NICOLAE, Silvia RADU, Nicoleta DOBROTĂ

ASB12. EXPERIMENTAL MODEL FOR ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF ELECTROMAGNETIC RADIATION ON BEES

Vasilică SAVU, Agripina ȘAPCALIU, Viorel FĂTU

ASB13. EFFECTS OF INCREASING LEVELS OF ANTHROPIZATION AND LAND USE ON NOSEMA SPP. SPORE LOADS

Cristina Gabriela MATHE, Tudor Nicolas TERNAR, Gianluca ALBANESE, Alexandru Ioan GIURGIU, Otilia BOBIȘ, Claudia PAȘCA, Melinda Maria TÓFALV, Antonio DE CRISTOFARO, Daniel Severus DEZMIREAN

10:45 – 11:00 COFFE BREAK

ASB14. ASSOCIATIVE EFFECTS OF *RODOTORULA GLUTINIS* YEAST x MULBERRY LEAVES ON THE MORPHO-PRODUCTIVE PARAMETERS OF TWO BREEDS OF SILKWORMS *BOMBYX MORY*

Mihaela HĂBEANU, Anca GHEORGHE, Adela Ramona MOISE, Mihaela DUMITRU, Nicoleta A. LEFTER, Melania F. ANDREI, Teodor MIHALCEA, Daniel Severus DEZMIREAN

ASB15. EFFECTS OF PROBIOTIC ADDITION TO MULBERRY LEAVES ON SILKWORM LARVAL AND COCOON TRAITS

Anca GHEORGHE, Mihaela HĂBEANU, Adela R. MOISE, Nicoleta A. LEFTER, Melania F. ANDREI, Teodor MIHALCEA, Daniel S. DEZMIREAN

ASB16. REVITALIZING ROMANIAN AGRICULTURE: INSIGHTS INTO PROPAGATION, UTILISATION AND GENETIC CONSERVATION OF MULBERRY

Ecaterina-Daniela BACIU, Adela-Ramona MOISE, Gabriela-Maria NEGREA-BACI, Daniel Severus DEZMIREAN

ASB17. THE INFLUENCING FACTORS OF PHEASANT MEAT CHARACTERISTICS: A REVIEW

Iuliana Ștefania (BOLOLOI) BORDEI, Georgiana Magdalena PÎRLEA, Elena Gabriela STAN, Ionela Florentina (ENACHE) TOMA, Andreea Ionela ZINCA, Roxana Elena (VASILIU) ȘTEFAN, Carmen Georgeta NICOLAE

ASB18. REDUCTION OF BUFFALO CHEESE VARIETY WITH ACTIVATED CHARCOAL

Andrada IHUȚ, Simona OROS, Simona PAȘCALĂU Cosmin OPRESCU, Eugen RĂDUCU, Camelia RĂDUCU

ASB19. EFFECTS OF FEEDING FERMENTED VS. UNFERMENTED RAPESEED CAKE ON THE THIGH MEAT QUALITY

Tatiana Dumitra PANAITE, Gabriela Maria CORNESCU, Mihaela DUMITRU, Dan RAMBU, Ana Elena CISMILEANU, Smaranda Mariana TOMA

ASB20. BIOMORPHOLOGY AND REGENERATION OF GENUS ACTINIDIA

Nina CIORCHINĂ, Maria TABĂRA, Natalia ONICA, Tatiana CALALB, Liliana BĂDULESCU, Oana VENAT, Ioana-Cătălina NICOLAE

ASB 21. EFFECTS OF RHIZOPHAGUS IRREGULARIS ON ECHINACEA PURPUREA ROOT BIOMASS AND PHENOLIC CONTENT

Martin IAKAB, Erzsébet DOMOKOS, Csilla ALBERT, Francisc Vasile DULF

ASB22. BUFORIN DERIVATIVES: SYNTHESIS AND ANTIMICROBIAL PROSPECTS

Andreea GOSTĂVICEANU, Cristian MOISĂ, Andreea LUPITU, Lucian COPOLOVICI, Dana-Maria COPOLOVICI

ASB23. CELL-PENETRATING PEPTIDES: MICROWAVE-ASSISTED SPPS SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION

Cristian MOISA, Andreea LUPITU, Lucian COPOLOVICI, Dana-Maria COPOLOVICI

ASB24. ANTIOXIDANT POTENTIAL OF MEDICINAL PLANT EXTRACTS

Lidia-Ioana VIRCHEA, Cecilia GEORGESCU, Monica MIRONESCU, Adina FRUM, Felicia GLIGOR

ASB25. AGRO-INDUSTRIAL BY-PRODUCTS MODULATE THE INTESTINAL MICROBIOTA COMPOSITION IN WEANING PIGLETS

Iulian Alexandru GROSU, Gina Cecilia PISTOL, Daniela Eliza MARIN, Ionelia TARANU

ASB26. PROBIOTIC LACTIC ACID BACTERIA STRAINS AS A KEY TO ENHANCING HONEYBEE HEALTH IN APICULTURE

Adriana Cristina URCAN, Adriana CRISTE, Alexandru GIURGIU, Daniel Severus DEZMIREAN

13:00 –13:10 – Closing ceremony and Best Posters Awards – AULA MAGNA “Mihai Serban”

Friday, 27th September, 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

Session 8: Veterinary Medicine - Fundamental and Preclinical Sciences

Hall: The Green Amphitheater - Life Sciences Institute

9:00 – 10:30 ORAL PRESENTATION

Chairman: Prof. Miguel MORENO MILLAN, PhD

Moderators: Prof. Sanda ANDREI, PhD

Secretary: Andreea MOROHOSCHI, PhD student

THE FIRST REPORT OF PRESUMED CANINE DISTEMPER VIRUS INCLUSION BODIES IN THE DENTAL PULP OF A DOG

Raluca-Ioana NEDELEA, Vasile RUS, Ioan MARCUS, Adrian Florin GAL

NEW APPROACH OF LABORATORY EXAM IN ACUTE PANCREATITIS IN DOG

Ioana-Mădălina MORARU, Alexandra-Iulia DREANCĂ, Orsolya SARPATAKI, Bogdan SEVASTRE, Ioan MARCUS

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF HEMERYTHRIN AND OVINE POLYMERIZED HEMOGLOBIN FOR VASCULAR AND SYSTEMIC EFFECTS IN A RAT HEMORRHAGIC SHOCK MODEL

Stefania-Madalina DANDEA, Vlad-Alexandru TOMA2, Alina HASAS, Maria LEHENE, Ioana ROMAN, Cristian MOLDOVEANU, Mircea MUNTEAN, Radu SILAGHI-DUMITRESCU, Bogdan SEVASTRE

ANIMAL MODELS DESIGNED FOR EXPERIMENTAL OSTEOMYELITIS

Oana ROTAR, Alexandra Iulia DREANCĂ, Klara MAGYARI, Alexandra FERARU, Bogdan SEVASTRE

ACUTE TOXICOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF *BETULA PENDULA* ROTH, *BETULA PUBESCENS* EHRH. IN MURINE MODELS

Alina Diana HASAS, Daniela HANGANU, Timea Henrietta DEZSO (BAB), Neli Kinga OLAH, Irina IELCIU, Raluca MARICA, Oana ROTAR, Teodora TANCIU, Bogdan SEVASTRE

10:30 – 11:00 COFFEE BREAK

11:00 – 12:30 POSTER PRESENTATION

POSTERS

MV1. THE NEPHROPROTECTIVE EFFECT OF CORNUS MAS AND SORBUS AUCUPARIA FRUIT EXTRACTS IN GENTAMICIN-INDUCED NEPHROTOXICITY IN WISTAR RATS

Mara AURORI, Alexandra Iulia DREANCĂ, Andreea Georgiana MOROHOSCHI, Mihaela COTUL, Adrian Florin GAL, Sanda ANDREI

MV2. NITROGEN BALANCE AND URIC ACID EXCRETION IN LOHMANN-BROWN HENS FED DIETS WITH DIFFERENT CRUDE PROTEIN AND METABOLIZABLE ENERGY LEVELS

Mădălina CIOARIC (DEGENARO), Rosalie BĂLĂCEANU, Andrei Tudor KACENCO, Ivona ZĂBAVĂ, Ilinca IOZON, Nicolae DOJANĂ

MV3. ARE EXOTIC PETS HIDING RESISTANT BUGS?

Smaranda CRĂCIUN, Cristiana Ștefania NOVAC, Zsuzsa KALMÁR, Cosmina BOUARI, Ioana Adriana MATEI, Nicodim Iosif FIȚ, George Cosmin NADĂȘ

MV4. MONITORING AND RISK ASSESSMENT OF PESTICIDE RESIDUES IN IMPORTED FRESH PRODUCE: A CASE STUDY ON TOMATOES AND EGGPLANTS

Gheorghe Valentin GORAN, Emanuela BADEA, Ionuț Răzvan DOBRE, Nicoleta CIOCÎRLIE

MV5. NON-REGENERATIVE ANEMIA – DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA IN DOGS

Alina Diana HASAS, Naëlle BERTHIAUX, Bogdan SEVASTRE

MV6. ANESTHESIA MANAGEMENT FOR SOFT TISSUE SURGERY IN BRACHYCEPHALIC PATIENTS

Iulia-Maria HEGER, Cosmin Petru PEȘTEAN, Ioan MARCUS

MV7. DSS-INDUCED ACUTE INTESTINAL INFLAMMATION IN RATS: HISTOLOGICAL FEATURES

Ilinca IOZON, Adrian-Florin GAL, Maria-Cătălina MATEI-LAȚIU, Vasile RUS, Laura Cristina ȘTEFĂNUȚ

MV8. *IN VITRO* STUDIES ON THE CYTOTOXIC EFFECTS OF METAMIZOLE, 4-METHYLAMINOANTIPYRINE AND 4-AMINOANTI-PYRINE ON LIVER CELL LINES

Georgiana-Iulia LUPU, Eموke PALL, Mihai CENARIU, Monica Irina NAN, Sanda ANDREI

MV9. ARE GILL RACKERS INVOLVED IN TASTE PERCEPTION AND FOOD INGESTION FOR GOBIO CARPATHICUS (VLADYKOV, 1925)? A DEBATE SUSTAINED BY HISTOLOGICAL ARGUMENTS

Maria-Catalina MATEI-LATIU, Calin LATIU, Vasile RUS, Adrian GAL

MV10. THERAPEUTIC USE OF TULATHROMYCIN IN OVINE BACTERIAL PATHOLOGIES, FIELD FINDINGS

Carmen Ramona MOLDOVAN, Mihai MADRU, Oana ROTAR, Lucie NICOLLE, Alexandra DREANCĂ, Smaranda CRACIUN, Ioana MATEI, Ioan MARCUS

MV11. BIOCHEMICAL EFFECTS OF DONKEY MILK CONSUMPTION IN MURINE MODELS

Andreea MOROHOSCHI, Sanda ANDREI

MV12. INSIGHT ON COCKER SPANIELS' EXTERNAL EAR MICROFLORA

Cristiana-Ștefania NOVAC, Dumitru TOLICO, Smaranda CRĂCIUN, George Cosmin NADĂȘ, Cosmina Maria BOUARI, Sorin RĂPUNTEAN, Nicodim Iosif FIȚ

MV13. A HIDDEN THREAT: A CASE REPORT ON PHEOCHROMOCYTOMA IN A HORSE (EQUUS FERUS CABALLUS)

Romelia POP, Dragoș HODOR, Cristian CRECAN, Iancu MORAR, Alexandru Florin LUPSAN, Zsofia DARADICS, Mirela Alexandra TRIPON, Denisa BUNGĂRDEAN, Otilia BULMEZ, Maria POPESCU, Valeria CIULU-ANGELESCU, Alexandru-Flaviu TĂBĂRAN

MV14. TOXICOKINETIC OF PLASTIC PARTICLES AFTER DIGESTIVE EXPOSURE IN RODENTS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

Paula-Raluca POPA, Alexandru Flaviu TĂBĂRAN

MV15. OXIDATIVE STRESS MARKERS IN ROMANIAN SPOTTED COWS AFFECTED BY RETAINED FETAL MEMBRANES

Horațiu RAFA, Oana Maria COZMA, Ioan OROIAN, Andreea Georgiana MOROHOSCHI, Daria Antonia DUMITRAȘ, Sanda ANDREI

MV16. THE IMPACT OF RETAINED FETAL MEMBRANES ON METABOLIC AND HORMONAL PROFILES IN ROMANIAN SPOTTED COWS

Horațiu RAFA, Oana Maria COZMA, Ioan OROIAN, Andreea Georgiana MOROHOSCHI, Daria Antonia DUMITRAȘ, Daniela NEAGU, Sanda ANDREI

MV17. THE USE OF INTRAVENOUS LIPID EMULSION FOR THE TREATMENT OF SMALL ANIMAL'S INTOXICATIONS

Oana ROTAR, Alexandra DREANĂ, Denisa SAND, Hélène GRAO, Dalma PIVARIU, Ioan MARCUS, Adrian Nechita OROS, Bogdan SEVASTRE

MV18. UNUSUAL MUSCLE-RELATED MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES DETECTED IN THE CRANIAL CAVA VEIN IN 10-DAY-OLD BROILER CHICKENS

Vasile RUS, Maria-Cătălina MATEI-LAȚIU, Adrian Florin GAL

MV19. BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES AND ACUT TOXICITY OF COMBRETUM MICRANTHUM

Ibrahima Mamadou SALL, TABARAN Alexandru-Flaviu, Alina Diana HASAS, Malek AMIALI

MV20. TO BLEED OR NOT TO BLEED: A THOROUGH REVIEW ON HEMOSTATIC AGENTS

O Denisa SAND, Alexandra DREANCA, Klara MAGYARI, Zsejke-Réka TOTH, Lucian BAIA, Ioan MARCUS

MV21. EFFICACY EVALUATION OF AN CANINE ANTHELMINTIC PRODUC BASED ON MILBEMYCIN OXIME AND PRAZIQUANTEL MOLECULE IN NATURAL INFECTED DOGS FROM HUNEDOARA COUNTRY

Diana TODORAN, Melania CRISAN, Octavia TAMAS-KRUMPE, Daria FENESAN, Laurent OGNEAN

**MV22. ESTROUS CYCLE LENGTH IN THE ALGERIAN ARBIA GOAT:
EXFOLIATIVE VAGINAL CYTOLOGY AND SERUM PROGESTERONE LEVELS**

Achour YAHIA, Nabila HAMMAMI, Khelaf SAIDANI, Khadidja HAMRAT, Nora
MIMOUNE

**MV23. A REVIEW ON THE USE OF ANTAGONIST MEDICATION IN FENTANYL
AND A2-ADRENERGIC AGONIST INTOXICATION**

Diana Bianca ZALISCHI, Mihai Sorin CERNEA

**13:00 –13:10 – Closing ceremony and Best Posters Awards – AULA MAGNA “Mihai
Serban”**

Friday, 27th September, 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

Session 9: Veterinary Medicine - Clinical Sciences

Hall: The Blue Amphitheater - Life Sciences Institute

09:00 – 10:30 ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Chairman: Assoc. Prof. Cosmin PEȘTEAN, PhD

Moderators: Assoc. Prof. Constatin CERBU, PhD

Secretary: Sergiu CONDOR, PhD student

ARE PHYTOTHERAPEUTICS THE FUTURE IN ATOPIC DERMATITIS? – A BIBLIOGRAPHIC REVIEW OF CANINE ATOPIC DERMATITIS AND ATOPIC DERMATITIS MODELS

Lorena-Eliza MASTAN, Bogdan SEVASTRE, Viorica MIRCEAN

NERVE STIMULATOR-ASSISTED BRACHIAL PLEXUS BLOCK IN RED-EARED SLIDERS (TRACHEMYS SCRIPTA ELEGANS) – A CASE REPORT

Alexandra CREȚ, Maria-Carmen TURCU, Iulia MELEGA, Lucia BEL, Cosmin PEȘTEAN, Mihai CENARIU

THE USE OF A PEDICLE FLAP OF THE GREATER OMENTUM AS AN ADJUVANT IN CHRONIC NON-HEALING WOUNDS: A CASE REPORT

Tom ABLASSMAIER, Alina ZĂVOI, Sidonia GOG-BOGDAN, Nicușor OROS, Liviu OANA, Lucia BEL

PRELIMINARY STUDY ON EVALUATION OF OCULOSCOPY USING THREE MIDRIATIC AGENTS IN RABBITS

Lucia BEL, Marie DUBOIS, Stefana MURESAN, Cosmina DEJESCU, Carmen Maria TURCU, Iulia MELEGA, Alexandra CREȚ, Sidonia GOG-BOGDAN

NOT ALL UTERINE PATHOLOGIES ARE ADENOCARCINOMAS: A CASE SERIES OF FOUR PET RABBITS (ORYCTOLAGUS CUNICULI)

Maria-Carmen TURCU, Iulia MELEGA, Alexandra CREȚ, Cosmina DEJESCU, Georgiana LUPU, Miruna MATEI, Felix LUCACI, Sorin MÎRZA, Andrada NEGOESCU, Romelia POP, Flaviu TABARAN and Lucia BEL

10:30 – 11:00 COFFEE BREAK

POSTERS

MV24. THE OSTEOINDUCTIVE POTENTIAL OF BIOPOLYMER-BASED GOLD NANOPARTICLE-CONTAINING BIOACTIVE GLASSES ON A COMPLICATION OF A TIBIAL FRACTURE IN DOG. CASE REPORT

Andreea Niculina AȘTILEAN (PERTEA), Alexandra DREANCĂ, Nicușor Valentin OROS, Sorin MÂRZA, Klara MAGYARI, Liviu OANA

MV25. HABITAT INFLUENCE ON TRACE ELEMENT STATUS IN CATS

Emanuela BADEA, Gheorghe Valentin GORAN, Oana Diana MIHAI, Carmen Daniela PETCU, Cristina ȚOCA

MV26. EPIDEMIOLOGY AND EVOLUTION OF FELINE BACTERIAL CYSTITIS: A RETROSPECTIVE STUDY

Anca BARBOS, Alexandra BIRIS, Mircea MIRCEAN, Radu LACATUS

MV27. PREVALENCE, RISK FACTORS, AND CLINICAL FEATURES OF THE MOST COMMON ENDOCRINE DISEASES IN DOGS – A LITERATURE REVIEW

Cristina BERINDEAN, Andrei Răzvan CODEA, Alina HASAS, Radu LĂCĂTUȘ

MV28. PREVALENCE, RISK FACTORS, AND CLINICAL FEATURES OF THE MOST COMMON ENDOCRINE DISEASES IN CATS – A LITERATURE REVIEW

Cristina BERINDEAN, Andrei Răzvan CODEA, Alina HASAS, Radu LĂCĂTUȘ

MV29. HERD HEALTH CONTROL AND ECONOMIC PARAMETERS OF SHEEP

Jovan BOJKOVSKI, Ivan PAVLOVIĆ, Milan NINKOVIĆ, Zsolt BECKEL, Ivan DOBROSAVLJEVIĆ, Jasna STEVNOVIĆ, Renata RELIĆ, Sveta ARSIĆ, Sreten NEDIĆ, Ivan VUJANAC, Aleksandra MITROVIĆ, Radiša PRODANOVIĆ, Branko Angelovski

MV30. FEATHER PICKING DISEASE IN PARROTS: A PREVALENT YET POORLY UNDERSTOOD BEHAVIOR IN AVIAN VETERINARY PRACTICE

Mariana-Gabriela BUMBU, Anca-Alexandra DOBOSI

MV31. EVALUATION OF A NOVEL CERVICAL VERTEBRAL FIXATION TECHNIQUE IN EQUINES BASED ON THE STABILIZATION OF THE FACET JOINTS

Valeria CIULU-ANGELESCU, Oana Liviu-Ioan OANA, Mirela-Alexandra TRIPON, Cristian Mihăiță CRECAN

MV32. DIAGNOSTIC UTILITY OF METHYLENE BLUE UPPER DIGESTIVE CHROMOENDOSCOPY IN DOGS

Andrei Răzvan CODEA, Andrei Paul COZMA, Alexandra BIRIȘ, Cristian POPOVICI, Daniela NEAGU, Mircea MIRCEAN

MV33. UTILITY OF URINARY N-ACETYL-B-D-GLUCOSAMINIDASE INDEX IN EARLY DETECTION OF ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY AMONG ROMANIAN BUFFALOES WITH PYELONEPHRITIS

Andrei Răzvan CODEA, Alexandra BIRIȘ, Cristian POPOVICI, Daniela NEAGU, Alexandra MUREȘAN, Hari Attila István, Mircea MIRCEAN

MV34. PRELIMINARY RESULTS REGARDING HOLTER MONITORING FINDINGS IN HEALTHY CATS

Alexandra COFARU, Raluca MURARIU, Iuliu Călin SCURTU

MV35. ASSESSMENT OF HYGIENIC QUALITY AND STAPHYLOCOCCUS SPP. PREVALENCE IN SMALL RUMINANT MILK

Sergiu CONDOR, Nicolas PILON, Raluca CÎMPEAN, Oana REGET, Sorin Daniel DAN, Marian MIHAIU, Laura CONDOR, Alexandra TABARAN

MV36. BRACHYCEPHALIC DENTAL ISSUES

Ana-Maria COSTIN, Petru Cosmin PEȘTEAN, Florin BETEG

MV37. COMPARISON OF JUGULAR AND SAPHENOUS BLOOD LACTATE CONCENTRATIONS AS A PROGNOSTIC MARKER IN DOGS WITH GASTRIC DILATATION AND VOLVULUS

Adria HERLE, Stefan SERBAN, Florin BETEG

MV38. IDENTIFICATION OF SOME PREDICTIVE BIOMARKERS IN UTERINE BITCHES DISEASES

Ioan Emilian HORVAT, Florin BETEG, Nicodim FIȚ, Mihai CENARIU

MV39. *CRYPTOSPORIDIUM* SPP. IN REPTILES: UNRAVELING DETECTION CHALLENGES AND MOLECULAR CHARACTERIZATION SIGNIFICANCE

Mariana LOURO, Laura HERNANDEZ, João ANTUNES, Luís MADEIRA DE CARVALHO, Isabel PEREIRA DA FONSECA, Jacinto GOMES

MV40. *IN VITRO* EFFICACY OF ALBENDAZOLE AND DORAMECTINE ON SHEEP GASTROINTESTINAL STRONGYLES

Virginia Ana MAGDAȘ, Cristian MAGDAȘ, Mihai Sorin CERNEA, Vasile COZMA

MV41. CANINE ATOPIC-LIKE DERMATITIS: A CLINICAL CASE

Lorena-Eliza MASTAN, Adriana GYÖRKE, Aurora-Livia URSACHE

MV42. PREVALENCE OF CARDIAC DISEASES IN DOGS AND CATS: RETROSPECTIVE STUDY (2022 - 2024)

George Cristian MAURER, Romain Pierre-Yves HUREL, Laura Cristina ȘTEFĂNUȚ

MV43. EVALUATING MAGNESIUM-BASED ALLOYS FOR BIOMEDICAL APPLICATIONS: *IN VITRO* BIOCOMPATIBILITY AND ESTABLISHING AN ANIMAL MODEL FOR *IN VIVO* TESTING

Maria-Cristina MORARU, Marius C. MANOLE, Gheorghe MARTA, Olga SORITAU, Dan VODNAR, Bogdan SEVASTRE

MV44. EPIDEMIOLOGY OF LEFT-TO-RIGHT PERSISTENT DUCTUS ARTERIOSUS IN DOGS OVER THE PAST 3 YEARS

Raluca MURARIU, Alexandra COFARU, Iuliu Călin SCURTU

MV45. EVALUATION OF BLOOD LACTATE IN VARIOUS SURGICAL CONDITIONS IN DOGS AND CATS

Alexandra Maria MUREȘAN, Cosmin MUREȘAN, Florin BETEG

MV46. EPIDEMIOLOGICAL AND CLINICAL ASPECTS IN CANINE SEBACEOUS ADENITIS

Alexandru-Constantin PINTILIE, Viorica MIRCEAN

MV47. INDICATIONS, TECHNIQUE AND RECOVERY IN PANCARPAL ARTHRODESIS IN DOGS

Bianca POP, Ciprian OBER

MV48. CORRELATIONS BETWEEN THE ADVANCED STAGES OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE AND NON-REGENERATIVE ANEMIA IN FELINES

Joana-Nicole REU, Iuliana CODREANU

MV49. ANNUAL REGIONAL PREVALENCE FOR TRICHINELLA SPP. IN BOAR MEAT IN SIBIU COUNTY

Șerban-Emilian ȚICHINDELEAN, Marian MIHAIU

13:00 –13:10 – Closing ceremony and Best Posters Awards – AULA MAGNA “Mihai Serban”

Friday, 27th September, 2024

DAILY PROGRAM SCHEDULE

Session 10: Geodesy, Forestry and Applied Exact Sciences

Hall: ICHAT Building – ground floor

09:00 – 13:00 POSTER SESSION (Presentation and evaluation)

Chairman: Mr. Nikola Vucic, PhD

Moderator: Prof. Ciprian George FORA, PhD

Assoc.Prof. Horia Dan VLASIN, PhD

Secretary: Assist. Mircea VARGA, PhD

FSC1. EARLY DETECTION OF BARK BEETLE INFESTATIONS OF SPRUCE STANDS, USING MULTISPECTRAL UAV IMAGERY. CASE STUDY FROM VALEA IERII, CLUJ COUNTY.

Vasile ŞIMONCA, Emanuel Elemer ŞUBA, Mircea Ioan VARGA, Alexandru COLIŞAR, Steluţa Maria SÎNGEORZAN, Florin Alexandru REBREAN, Tudor SĂLĂGEAN, Horia Dan VLASIN

13:00 –13:10 – Closing ceremony and Best Posters Awards – AULA MAGNA “Mihai Serban”

SATURDAY, 28th September 2024

Post -Conference Tour (optional)

The trip organized on Saturday 28 September 2024 for the participants in the International Conference Life Sciences for Sustainable Development at Vinea Apoldia Maior Fest - 3rd edition!

Distance 170 km on the highway destination Apold, Sibiu county including one stop in Alba Iulia, to visit the Carolina Fortress.

Departure at 8.30 a.m. by university bus from the University Campus, Department of Mechanization (behind the Aula Building). Return in the evening around 21.00 to the university campus.

USAMV Cluj-Napoca is the welcoming host of wine, traditional dishes and quality music lovers! As usual, at the Vinea Apoldia Maior Fest you will enjoy performances, fragrant wine tastings, stories about the history of the place, spectacular photos in the vineyard and delicious food! We are looking forward to welcoming you in Apoldu de Sus (Sibiu county), to spend an unforgettable day in our vineyard, together with the USAMV Cluj-Napoca community, its friends and partners! It is in this special place, steeped in its history of a long wine-growing tradition, that a noble vine plantation has been established on an area of 65 hectares. Pink Traminer, Italian Riesling, Sauvignon Blanc, Pinot Gris and Muscat Ottonel are the grape varieties skilfully cultivated at **Vinea Apoldia Maior**.

Since 2020, the **vineyard Vinea Apoldia Maior** is part of the patrimony of **the USAMV Cluj-Napoca**, so the academic process can be multi-dimensional. The vineyard is the ideal place to unravel the mysteries of oenology, viticulture or other specializations such as pedology, plant pathology or agricultural machinery. A place for learning, where in addition to research and innovation, grapes are masterfully transformed into tasty Bahian liqueurs. The wines from the winery of the [Vinea Apoldia Maior - USAMV Cluj-Napoca vineyard](#) combine the long local tradition with the modernity of vine cultivation, the specificity of the soils and unique microclimate conditions with the refinement of special cultivars of noble varieties, the science with the love and patience of our specialists. With vibrant aromas of tropical fruit, elderflower and grapefruit, our Sauvignon Blanc from the Academicum 2023 range is a Sauvignon Blanc that has already received countless awards: Gold Medal at Catavinum in Spain 2024, Silver Medal at Concours Mondial de Bruxelles 2024, Gold Medal at Winelovers Wine Awards, Hungary, 2024. Its aromatic notes stand out distinctly, the palate is vigorous, full-flavored, with prominent notes of mango and grapefruit and an aftertaste of green apple. Five labels of wines produced in 2023 at the Vinea Apoldia Maior Vineyard, awarded at the Winelovers Wine Awards in Budapest!

Alba Iulia is one of the earliest settlements in the country, which was known as "**Apulum**" during the Roman occupation. Back then, it was the largest economic and military center. Tatar invasions in 1241 destroyed the city, but its glory was recovered when it became **the capital of the Principality of Transylvania** (1542 - 1690). **Alba Iulia** was the first capital of the three Romanian provinces (**Walla Wallachia, Transylvania and Moldavia**), an action taken by **Michael the Brave**, laying the foundations of an ideal for which Romanians have fought throughout the ages. Let's suppose you arrived in Alba Iulia by car and followed the road to the city center. Everyone you tell on the way back to **Alba Iulia** will ask you without hesitation: "**Did you visit the Citadel**"? We tell you that by visiting the largest fortress in Romania you will discover that it is possible to go back in time. Not an imaginary one, not even the physical,

classic, known time that the scientists were talking about, but a time of finding oneself in a place where history has had the courage to be reborn and live again in the present. So get ready! Don't forget your camera or cell phone. The bastion fortification of Alba Iulia is **the largest fortress in Romania**, which has been standing for more than 300 years. **The fortress is the place where you can go back in time**, over two millennia, among the remains of three fortifications from as many different eras. In other words, each fortress built here incorporated the old one: The castle built by the Romans, the medieval citadel and the citadel of Alba Carolina. The **latter** was built in Alba Iulia **in the early 18th century**. **The fortification was first designed** by the Italian architect Giovanni Morando Visconti, who also supervised the first phase of the works. The architect died of the plague and rests in the Roman Catholic Cathedral in Alba Iulia. **The foundation stone of the Citadel** was laid on November 4, 1715. Broadly speaking, the year of its completion is considered to be 1738, although there were various works in later years.

The fortification, **designed on an area of 110 hectares**, with an enclosure defended by three rows of walls, **was given a stellate shape**, with seven bastions alternating with six ravelins, crossed by vaulted galleries, all bounded by deep ditches. The **shape of a seven-pointed star** is the result of the **seven bastions**, which form the most important and best protected 'security enclosure' of the fortification in the central area. The walls of the bastions are 2.5 meters thick and over 10 meters high. The fortress built in the heart of Transylvania has proved to be **the most imposing Baroque monument** in the province. **A particular feature of the fortress** is the sequence of the six gates, situated on an east-west axis. The imposing fortification **was named after the Emperor Charles VI**, as it was built during his reign, or Carlsburg - Charles's Citadel. **The role of the Citadel** was a military, defensive one, given the bastion system, the type of artillery, as well as the size of the troops inside it. The fortress was attacked once in its military existence, but never conquered. The episode took place in 1849, when 8,000 Hungarian soldiers besieged unsuccessfully.

Alba Carolina Citadel has undergone spectacular transformations in recent years, making it increasingly visible on the tourist map of Europe. In parallel with the restoration works, co-financed by European funds, it was also intended to enhance its exceptional cultural heritage. The fortress is the venue for cultural festivals, famous orchestras and concerts by top Romanian and foreign artists.

Have a wonderful day!

YOUR NOTES

the **23**rd INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
**LIFE SCIENCES FOR
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